

A matter of choice: Raw material specialisation at the Middle Pleistocene kill-butchered site of Gran Dolina TD10.2 (Atapuerca, Spain)

andion.arteaga@gmail.com (Andion Arteaga-Briebe) *Corresponding author / ORCID: 0000-0001-7484-962X

marina.mosquera@urv.cat (Marina Mosquera) / ORCID: 0000-0003-4823-6154

aolle@iphes.cat (Andreu Ollé) / ORCID: 0000-0002-8643-5536

Filiations:

1. Centro Nacional de Investigación sobre la Evolución Humana (CENIEH), Paseo de Atapuerca 3, 09002, Burgos, Spain.
2. Institut Català de Paleoecologia Humana i Evolució Social (IPHES-CERCA), Zona Educacional 4, Campus Sescelades URV (Edifici W3), 43007, Tarragona, Spain.
3. Departament d'Història i Història de l'Art, Universitat Rovira i Virgili, Avinguda de Catalunya 35, 43002, Tarragona, Spain.

This is the accepted version of an article published in *Quaternary International*. The final version is available at:

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quaint.2026.110221>

Please cite the published version.

Recommended citation:

Arteaga-Briebe, A., Mosquera, M., & Ollé, A. (2026). A matter of choice: Raw material specialisation at the Middle Pleistocene kill-butchered site of Gran Dolina TD10.2 (Atapuerca, Spain). *Quaternary International*, 765, 110221.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quaint.2026.110221>

Abstract

The Sierra de Atapuerca (Burgos, Spain) offers a rich diversity and abundance of abiotic resources which, coupled with its strategic location as a natural transit route and ecological crossroads, has contributed to the high concentration of archaeological sites in the area. The Pleistocene archaeological deposits of Atapuerca exhibit a relatively

uniform raw material procurement pattern, primarily focused on the exploitation of local chert from the summit and slopes of the ridge, and quartzite, sandstone, and quartz from the surrounding fluvial terraces.

The TD10.2-BB sublevel of Gran Dolina is, however, an exception. Interpreted as a monospecific bison kill-butcherer site, this deposit reveals an almost exclusive reliance on chert, indicating a raw material selection strategy unparalleled in other Atapuerca contexts.

This study revisits traditional hypotheses regarding lithic procurement to explore the factors underlying this distinctive pattern. Our analysis suggests that the predominance of chert in TD10.2-BB reflects a targeted adaptation in the use of resources, with raw material procurement shifting from fluvial terraces to the Sierra's uplands. We propose that this strategy is closely linked to the site's functional role as a specialised kill-butcherer location and the distribution of bison herds during hunting events.

Ultimately, this case illustrates the complex interplay between lithic resource management, technological choices, and social organisation. The raw material specialisation observed in TD10.2-BB exemplifies the adaptive strategies of the group occupying this Middle Pleistocene site, tying their resource procurement dynamics and technological decisions to the functional requirements of subsistence tasks and the prevailing ecological and environmental conditions.

Key words: Lithic raw material procurement; Kill-butcherer site; Gran Dolina; Chert; Middle Pleistocene.

1. INTRODUCTION

Raw material procurement is a central aspect of reconstructing the organisational strategies of past human groups, providing critical insights into their settlement systems, mobility patterns, and interaction with the environment (Geneste, 1991; Andrefsky, 1994; Browne and Wilson, 2011; Turq et al., 2013; Garvey, 2015; Agam, 2020). The selection of specific lithic resources within the landscape is seldom arbitrary, but reflects a complex decision-making process, shaped by the dynamic synergies between technological requirements, environmental conditions, and sociocultural considerations.

Understanding the rationale behind raw material selection requires a comprehensive assessment of the circumstances that could either constrain or favour particular choices. This involves exploring how these different factors interact to determine procurement strategies and identifying the underlying causal mechanisms that made certain sources or materials more advantageous or desirable than others.

The drivers governing raw material procurement are generally determined by geographical (environmental), geological (physical), and human (behavioural) considerations. Within this framework, provisioning strategies are often conceptualised in terms of cost-effectiveness (Binford, 1979; Bamforth, 1986; Brantingham, 2003; Browne and Wilson, 2011; Garvey, 2015). According to the principles of optimal foraging theory (Pyke et al., 1977; Smith et al., 1983; Pyke, 1984; Bird and O'Connell, 2006; Kelly, 2013), lithic acquisition is assumed to be guided by energy-efficient logics aimed at maximising returns under given environmental and contextual conditions (Dibble, 1991; Brantingham, 2003; Li et al., 2016; Pop et al., 2022).

Central variables in this model include distance to raw material sources (Renfrew, 1977; Nelson, 1991; Metcalfe and Barlow, 1992; Newman, 1994; Andrefsky, 2008; Wilson et al., 2018), topography and accessibility (Findlow and Bolognese, 1982; Wilson, 2007a; Asryan et al., 2014; Lucero et al., 2021), resource availability and abundance (Bamforth, 1986; Goodyear, 1993; Andrefsky, 1994; Hiscock, 2009; Soto et al., 2018), and the physical effort required (Ataman et al., 1992; Elston, 1994; Beck et al., 2002; Wilson, 2007a; Wilson and Browne, 2014).

From this perspective, the raw materials represented at a given site reflect a set of decisions guided by a principle of cost minimisation, in terms of energy, time or logistics. While each factor plays its own part in the decision-making process, it is their context-dependent interactions that ultimately generate adaptive group responses. Under this lens, Binford's influential distinction between embedded and direct procurement strategies (1979) has served as a conceptual axis underpinning the interpretation of lithic supply. This dichotomy has traditionally shaped the way researchers interpret the logistics of raw material procurement (Agam and Finkel, 2024). Yet these two concepts are better conceived not as mutually exclusive, but as flexible parts of a continuum that reflects the behavioural variability of hominin groups.

This organisational dimension also intersects with technological expression. There are discernible, albeit somewhat simplified, correlations between raw material variables and the organisation of lithic technology, intended to minimise risks and optimise mobility and technological strategies (Torrence, 1989; Meignen et al., 2009; Vaquero and Romagnoli, 2018). For instance, increased distances from raw material sources are often correlated with the development of personal toolkits and the adoption of formally designed curated technologies, focusing on efficient resource use, adaptability to varying situations, and resilience against failure (Binford, 1979; Bamforth, 1986; Bleed, 1986; Torrence, 1989; Nelson, 1991; Kuhn, 1994). Similarly, resource scarcity and high procurement costs often foster adaptive technological responses designed to maximise efficiency and ensure reliability under constrained conditions.

Beyond economic considerations, the physical properties of raw materials play a decisive role in the selection process (Andrefsky, 1994; Browne and Wilson, 2011; Schmidt et al., 2024; Nora et al., 2025). These properties include external attributes such as size and shape (Ditchfield, 2016), as well as internal characteristics like grain size, fracture predictability, toughness, and homogeneity. The latter attributes determine the material's suitability for knapping and the durability and performance of the resultant edges (Shick, 1987; Stout et al., 2005; Braun et al., 2009; Abrunhosa et al., 2019; Key et al., 2024; Schmidt et al., 2024).

Traditionally, it has been implicitly assumed that the capacity to execute formal technological designs is limited by the quality of the lithic material (Luedtke, 1992; Brantingham et al., 2000). This has, however, been contested by researchers who contend that the influence of raw materials on technical performance is less decisive than previously thought (e.g., Eren et al., 2014). They hold that the success of technological designs is more largely reliant on the knapper's skill and expertise, shifting the focus from the limitations imposed by raw material constraints to the knapper's adaptability and flexibility in overcoming them (Sharon, 2008; Eren et al., 2011; Romagnoli et al., 2017). Furthermore, as Mears and Wilson (2023, p. 3) point out, the notion of quality should be approached with caution, as it ultimately depends on the knapper's specific needs and the intended purpose of the tool.

There are other aspects linked to human agency that often remain elusive, as they cannot be fully explained through models of cost-benefit optimisation, environmental determinism, or strictly technical and functional requirements (Wilson, 2007b; Conneller,

2012; Agam, 2020). Decisions surrounding raw material selection could reflect factors that extend beyond purely pragmatic considerations. These include social and cultural dimensions (Gould and Saggars, 1985), where different cultural groups build diverse traditions into their interactions with raw materials (Moncel and Daujeard, 2012; Agam, 2020), and symbolic and aesthetic values that shaped how and why certain resources were chosen (Taçon, 1991; Assaf, 2018). In some instances, even personal preferences or idiosyncrasies, such as a particular attachment to a given lithology, may have influenced these choices.

Additionally, more intangible variables, such as landscape knowledge, mobility patterns, foresight and planning capabilities, direction of travel, group size, subsistence needs, time constraints, social dynamics, territorial boundaries, and networks of cultural exchange, should be considered for a full understanding of how prehistoric societies acquired and used lithic resources (Torrence, 1983; 1989; Wilson, 2007b; Tomasso and Porraz, 2016; Clark and Linares-Matás, 2021; Pop et al., 2022). Moreover, these behaviours must be interpreted in relation to site function and the specific role each location played within the group's broader subsistence system.

We must also contend with the intrinsic challenges posed by the temporal resolution of the archaeological record (Bailey, 2007; Lucas, 2012; Perreault, 2019). It is often difficult, if not impossible, to determine whether the presence of specific raw materials reflects a single procurement event driven by a particular requirement, or whether it represents the cumulative outcome of diverse moments, tasks, and decisions (Wilson, 2011; Sossa-Ríos et al., 2024).

To summarise, the complex, multicausal nature of raw material procurement poses a major interpretative challenge: determining whether the occurrence of specific lithologies within an assemblage reflects arbitrary and opportunistic behaviours or deliberate technological planning. Addressing this question requires analytical frameworks that include environmental, material, and behavioural dimensions. It also depends on well-constrained and stratigraphically coherent sites, which allow behavioural variability to be assessed within cumulative, time-averaged Pleistocene archaeological records.

In this regard, the Sierra de Atapuerca (Burgos, northern Iberian Peninsula) offers an exceptional comparative framework that meets these analytical requirements. Its well-characterised geological context, the abundance and accessibility of lithic resources, and

a long, continuous record of human occupation provide ideal conditions for diachronic analysis (Rodríguez et al., 2011). This combination of environmental stability and resource diversity allows us to control for external variables and more precisely isolate factors potentially underlying procurement shifts, whether they arise from adaptive responses, logistical constraints, or culturally mediated choices.

In general, the Pleistocene assemblages from Atapuerca exhibit consistent raw material procurement strategies, predominantly based on the exploitation of local chert, quartzite, sandstone, quartz, and limestone (Ollé et al., 2013; Carbonell et al., 2014). In contrast, the TD10.2 subunit of the Gran Dolina site, particularly the TD10.2-BB sublevel, deviates markedly from this trend, showing a pronounced preference for chert, leading to a nearly monospecific procurement pattern.

This reliance on chert, despite the availability of diverse raw materials in the surrounding environment, represents a notable divergence from regional patterns that cannot be adequately accounted for by cost-benefit considerations alone. This distinctive behaviour raises critical questions about the underlying decision-making processes: To what extent does the preferential use of chert reflect specific functional advantages tailored to particular activities? Could cultural factors and group traditions have played a significant role in guiding this selective procurement? Furthermore, might these patterns be indicative of temporal changes in landscape utilisation or shifts in mobility strategies?

This study presents the raw material procurement patterns identified at TD10.2-BB, examining how specific subsistence behaviours shaped lithic management strategies in this particular context. By situating these patterns within the broader Atapuerca sequence, this contribution offers a detailed regional case study that helps refine ongoing discussions on raw material selection and resource management during the Middle Pleistocene.

1.1. The Sierra de Atapuerca and its lithological landscape

The Sierra de Atapuerca is a low-relief ridge located on the northern sub-plateau of the Iberian Peninsula, at the foothills of the Palaeozoic massif of Sierra de la Demanda. This geological formation corresponds to an overturned anticline, primarily composed of Upper Cretaceous limestones and dolomites (Turonian-Lower Santonian), overlaid by syntectonic Oligocene-Lower Miocene deposits (Olivé et al., 1990; Pineda and Arce, 1997; Ortega Martínez, 2009). In its northernmost sector, faulting and erosion have

exposed Triassic Keuper facies and Lower Jurassic dolomites and limestones. Towards the east, early Cretaceous formations crop out at the surface, including limestones, sandstones, and conglomerates associated with the Wealden facies, as well as Albian sands, clays, and deposits belonging to the Utrillas facies (Olivé et al., 1990; Pineda and Arce, 1997; Benito-Calvo and Pérez-González, 2015).

The formation of the Sierra and its associated karst system resulted from a succession of tectonic events, erosion and sedimentation episodes, and subsequent fluvial dynamics that shaped the present landscape (Ortega Martínez, 2009). These processes have also driven the incision of the regional drainage network, mainly comprising the Arlanzón River and its tributaries, the Vena and the Pico. This geomorphological evolution has produced a stepped sequence of 14 fluvial terraces and the formation of the multilevel karst system that constitutes the Atapuerca endokarst (Benito-Calvo and Pérez-González, 2007; Ortega Martínez, 2009; Benito-Calvo et al., 2017; 2018).

Within this karst system, Pleistocene sediments preserve a rich archaeological record documenting human occupation at several sites, including Gran Dolina, Galería, Sima del Elefante, Cueva Fantasma, Galería de las Estatuas, and Sima de los Huesos (Carbonell et al., 2014; Ortega et al., 2014; Arsuaga et al., 2017). Together, these sites attest to hominin presence over roughly 1.2-1.4 million years (Carbonell et al., 2008; Huguet et al., 2025), offering key insights into human evolution and settlement dynamics in the region (Rodríguez et al., 2011; Carbonell et al., 2014).

The Sierra de Atapuerca exhibits a rich lithological diversity, providing an abundant supply of abiotic resources (Carbonell et al., 1999; Mallol, 1999; García-Antón and Mosquera, 2007; Navazo et al., 2008; Ollé et al., 2013; García-Antón, 2016b; 2016a). Within this area, five primary knappable rock types have been identified, all of which are found in varying proportions across the archaeological assemblages: chert (Neogene and Cretaceous), quartzite, sandstone, quartz, and limestone (see Table 1). These materials, which include several subvarieties, are available within a radius of approximately 5 km from the Pleistocene archaeological sites, occurring in both primary and sub-primary position on the highlands and slopes of Atapuerca, and at secondary outcrops within the surrounding fluvial terraces (Figure 1). This distribution ensures an immediate local supply of lithic resources (*sensu* Geneste, 1988; 1991).

Neogene chert is the predominant lithic material in the vicinity of the archaeological sites. This formation is dated to the Late Miocene (Pineda and Arce, 1997). It exhibits considerable internal variability, largely due to diagenetic processes influenced by the sediment's position relative to the depocentre of the evaporitic lacustrine basin, particularly during phases of desiccation or water-level regression. As a result, different lithotypes have been identified, each with distinct macroscopic and petrographic characteristics contingent on the nature and extent of silica replacement (Soto et al., 2021).

Neogene chert is primarily exposed along the eastern slope of Sierra de Atapuerca, resulting from the erosion of the Astaracian marls and marly limestones along the Neogene margin of the Duero endorreic basin (Ollé et al., 2013). It typically occurs in the form of blocks, ranging in size from centimetric to metric and requiring an initial phase of blank preparation before transport.

This chert generally exhibits considerable heterogeneity, with textural variations, internal geodes, and surface alterations (Ollé et al., 2013; de Lombera-Hermida et al., 2020). Despite this variability, it is characterised by medium to high suitability for knapping, due to its relative softness and low fracture resistance. Experimental studies indicate its potential for producing large cutting edges with high resistance and cutting capacity (Terradillos-Bernal and Rodríguez-Álvarez, 2017). Its relative quality, workability, abundance, and lack of volumetric constraints contribute to its prevalence in the archaeological record.

Cretaceous chert is represented by three distinct formations (García-Antón et al., 2002; García-Antón, 2016a). The Rasa de San Vicente (RSV) outcrop corresponds to the Turonian-Lower Santonian formation (Olivé et al., 1990; Pineda and Arce, 1997). It is located in the elevated southeastern sector of Sierra de Atapuerca, covering an area of less than 0.02 km². It is located within 1 km of the Trincheras del Ferrocarril archaeological sites, thus providing almost immediate access to raw materials for the inhabitants of Atapuerca. RSV chert occurs both in primary and sub-primary positions, appearing as nodules, exposed as the limestone pavement broke down due to the dissolution of the enclosing Cretaceous limestone, a process that facilitated procurement (García-Antón, 2016a). The same formation is also present in primary position within the Atapuerca karstic system, specifically along the walls and ceiling of the Galería del Sílex (Ortega Martínez, 2009). However, due to its location, limited accessibility, and the difficulty of

extraction, it is unlikely that this source was exploited during the Pleistocene (Gabarró et al., 1999).

The nodules from RSV exhibit irregular morphologies, ranging from 10 to 20 cm in size. They are characterised by a slightly porous, rough, siliceous cortex. The matrix displays a microsparitic bioclastic texture of wackestone-packstone type, with notable moldic porosity and a high concentration of bioclasts, particularly near the cortex (García-Antón, 2016a; 2016b). These chert nodules generally show signs of weathering, primarily associated with freeze-thaw processes, resulting in gelifraction, potlids, and internal fissures. As a result, they often appear as fragments rather than complete nodules.

The second Cretaceous chert outcrop is known as Valdecuende (VDC), and belongs to the Turonian–Lower Santonian formation (Olivé et al., 1990; Pineda and Arce, 1997). It is located in the central sector of Sierra de Atapuerca, in the Valdecuende Valley headwaters, within the archaeological area known as Valle de las Orquídeas (Mosquera et al., 2007). The deposit covers an area of approximately 0.04 km² and is aligned with the erosive path created by the Pico River.

VDC chert is also found in the dolines of the area known as Campo de Brujas, situated in the upper part of the Sierra de Atapuerca. As in the case of RSV, VDC nodules have been exposed by the erosion of the limestone pavement surface.

VDC nodules are small, ranging from 5 to 15 cm, and display irregular morphologies with a tendency towards lentil-shaped and ovoid forms. The siliceous cortex is porous and fine-grained. The matrix exhibits a mudstone texture, with relatively limited moldic porosity, and contains various bioclasts, particularly spicules, foraminifera, and, to a lesser extent, crinoids and radiolarians (García-Antón, 2016a; 2016b). Like the RSV chert, the surfaces of the VDC nodules are impacted by gelifraction processes, resulting in the formation of macro and micro potlids. However, the surfaces do not exhibit significant granulation, due to the low porosity of this chert.

Lastly, Arlanzón chert (ARZ) corresponds to the Lower Cretaceous Wealden facies (Upper Valanginian – Lower Barremian) (Olivé et al., 1990). This facies appears in the southeastern sector of the Sierra de Atapuerca, approximately 6-7 km from the archaeological sites, making it the most distant outcrop in the study area. ARZ chert

occurs as nodules in primary position within the host limestone, or in sub-primary position as a result of erosional processes.

These nodules are heterometric, reaching up to 20 cm in diameter. They exhibit a brownish-black colour with an irregular and poorly developed cortex, often displaying a greyish internal hue. The sedimentary matrix is classified as mudstone–wackestone and contains characeans, oogonia, and ostracods (García-Antón, 2016a; 2016b). ARZ nodules have a high incidence of recrystallised fractures, which leads to fragmentation and the frequent occurrence of small, angular fragments.

Except for the Arlanzón chert, which is located at a greater distance and has limited presence in the archaeological context, both RSV and VDC Cretaceous formations are within 2 km of the archaeological sites. These outcrops provide fine-grained and relatively homogeneous siliceous materials that generally exhibit medium to high suitability for knapping (Terradillos-Bernal and Rodríguez-Álvarez, 2014). The resulting knapping products have resistant and regular edges, making them efficient for longitudinal and transverse movement (Terradillos-Bernal and Rodríguez-Álvarez, 2017). Nevertheless, Cretaceous chert is considerably less abundant in the landscape than Neogene chert resources, and the small size of their nodules, especially in the case of VDC, can pose significant constraints on knapping goals.

In addition to chert, the Sierra de Atapuerca and its surrounding environment provide access to a variety of lithic materials from two different sources: the fluvial terraces of the Arlanzón and Vena rivers and the Utrillas facies materials.

The fluvial terraces T7ARZ–T10ARZ, dated to the Middle Pleistocene (Moreno et al., 2012), surround the Sierra de Atapuerca and contain quartzite, sandstone, and quartz derived from the Palaeozoic formations of the nearby Sierra de la Demanda (Benito-Calvo, 2004; García-Antón, 2016a). These materials are available within a radius of approximately 1 km from the archaeological sites.

Quartzites, including quartzarenite, orthoquartzite, and metaquartzite, typically occur as large cobbles with irregular or quadrangular morphologies. They are generally fine-grained and homogeneous, displaying medium to high knapping quality (Ollé et al., 2013). However, as noted by Terradillos and Rodríguez-Álvarez (2017, p. 217), thick cortical surfaces may inhibit the efficient transmission of force during knapping. In

contrast, in fine-grained quartzites, thin convex cortical surfaces can facilitate fracture initiation.

Figure 1. Synthetic map showing the main raw material outcrop areas in Sierra de Atapuerca during the Middle Pleistocene, modified from Ollé et al. (2013, fig. 5) and García-Antón (2016a, A2). (a) Gypsiferous Neogene chert in secondary position; (b) quartzite and sandstone cobbles arranged on a Pleistocene terrace of the Arlanzón River; (c) detail of a quartzite cobble from the Utrillas facies; (d) image of the dismantled karst pavement located at Campo de las Brujas, with a detail of a VDC Cretaceous nodule; (e) detail of an RSV Cretaceous fragmented nodule recovered from the Alto de San Vicente; (f) Arlanzón Cretaceous chert nodule. Photographs by Andreu Ollé (a, d, e), Paola García-Medrano (b, c), and Dolores García-Antón (f).

Sandstones, a generic label including sandstone, metasandstone, and certain varieties of schist, are commonly found as small to medium-sized cobbles. These materials are characterised by a soft, homogeneous texture and a fine to medium grain size (Ollé et al., 2013). Despite these properties, their workability is considered moderate due to the frequent presence of internal fractures, which tend to generate numerous accidental breakages during exploitation. Experimental analyses have demonstrated the need to employ wide percussion platforms to effectively knap this material. Although the resulting edges are sharp, their friability significantly limits their durability and cutting efficiency (Terradillos-Bernal and Rodríguez-Álvarez, 2017).

Quartz appears at lower frequencies within the fluvial terraces and is represented by small pebbles with coarse macroscopic grain (de Lomberra-Hermida et al., 2011; 2020). The presence of internal fissures and structural irregularities makes this material quite unpredictable during knapping, often resulting in irregular and poorly controlled edges, thereby limiting its overall workability (Ollé et al., 2013; Terradillos-Bernal and Rodríguez-Álvarez, 2017).

The Arenas de Utrillas formation is located approximately 3 km northeast of the Trincheras archaeological sites (Pineda and Arce, 1997; García-Antón and Mosquera, 2007; García-Antón, 2016a). This formation contains small quartz pebbles and medium- to large-sized quartzite cobbles, typically displaying ellipsoidal to sub-spherical morphologies (Pedernana et al., 2017). Quartzites from the Utrillas facies are characterised by good knapping properties, producing blanks with regular morphologies and highly resistant edges (Ollé et al., 2013; Terradillos-Bernal and Rodríguez-Álvarez, 2014). Nevertheless,

coarse-grained and globular cobbles can be excessively tough and exhibit internal flaws that limit their flaking efficiency. (Terradillos-Bernal and Rodríguez-Álvarez, 2014).

Finally, limestone artefacts are also present in the archaeological record. This limestone originates directly from the Cretaceous substratum of the Sierra de Atapuerca and occurs both within the karstic system and on the surrounding surface (Ollé et al., 2013; García-Antón, 2016a). Its ubiquitous availability and geological context sometimes hinder the identification of its potentially anthropogenic nature (Terradillos-Bernal et al., 2022).

These autochthonous limestones have become detached from cave walls and ceilings, and are irregular clasts of limited suitability for knapping (Terradillos-Bernal and Rodríguez-Álvarez, 2014; Terradillos-Bernal et al., 2022). However, their immediate availability within the sites themselves represents a significant advantage (Mosquera et al., 2018).

Altogether, the lithological diversity of the Sierra de Atapuerca provided prehistoric groups with a wide range of raw materials, whose abundance, quality, and physical properties are likely to have favoured recurrent human occupation throughout the Pleistocene.

Raw material	Distance from sites	Abundance	Blank format	Blank Size	Knapping quality	Qualitative edge sharpness	Qualitative edge durability
Neo. Chert	From 1 km	High	Blocks and angular fragments	Large to very large (>100 cm)	Moderate to high	High	High
Cret. Chert*	From 0.5 to 2 km	Low	Nodules and sub-angular fragments	VDC (<10cm) RSV (<20 cm)	High	High	High
Quartzite**	From 1 to 3 km	High	Rounded cobbles	Medium to small	Moderate to high	Moderate	Moderate
Sandstone	From 1 km	High	Rounded to subflat cobbles	Medium to small	Moderate	Low	Low
Quartz	From 1 to 3 km	Medium	Rounded subspherical pebbles/cobbles	Pebbles and small cobbles	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate
Limestone	<1km	High	Angular fragments and cobbles	Heterogeneous fragments	Moderate	Low	Low

*Table 1. Summary of the main characteristics of the raw materials found in the Middle Pleistocene sites of Atapuerca. Modified from Ollé et al. (2013, p. 114) and Terradillos-Bernal et al. (2017, p. 217; 2022). *Cretaceous chert includes RSV and VDC varieties. **Quartzite and Sandstone are employed as broad categories encompassing several lithological types that cannot be reliably distinguished at the macroscopic scale.*

1.2. The archaeological site of Gran Dolina TD10.2

The subunit TD10.2 is located within the Gran Dolina site and forms part of TD10, the uppermost archaeological unit of the sequence (Figure 2). This unit comprises four distinct subunits (TD10.4 to TD10.1 from bottom to top). Chronometric dating has yielded ESR/U-series ages of 418 ± 63 ka and 337 ± 51 ka for the upper part of TD10.2 (Falguères et al., 1999; 2001), whereas ESR dating on quartz from the middle and basal part of the subunit provides dates of 375 ± 37 ka and 378 ± 10 ka (Moreno et al., 2015). A more recent Bayesian chronostratigraphic model integrating these datasets constrains the formation of TD10.2 to between 424 and 405 ka (Warnitz et al., 2025). However, a discordant OSL date suggests a younger mean age of 244 ± 26 ka (Berger et al., 2008).

Archaeostratigraphic analyses have identified three distinct archaeological sublevels within TD10.2, from bottom to top: TD10.2.2, TD10.2-Bison Bed (TD10.2-BB), and Upper TD10.2, each reflecting varying occupational intensities and functional characteristics (Arteaga-Briebe et al., 2023).

Figure 2. a) Location of Gran Dolina and Sierra de Atapuerca, in the North of the Iberian Peninsula; b) Gran Dolina's palaeomorphology from the railway trench (south

archaeological section) and main lithostratigraphic units; c) Synthetic sedimentary facies column of Gran Dolina site and location of available dates for TD10 (Berger et al., 2008; Falguères et al., 1999; Moreno et al., 2015). (Figures modified from Campaña et al., 2017, p. 79; Duval et al., 2022, p. 2; Rodríguez-Hidalgo et al., 2017, p. 91; Arteaga-Briebe et al. 2023, Fig.1).

Among these, TD10.2-BB is the most substantial sublevel in the sequence, accounting for over 75% of the total material recovered from TD10.2 (Arteaga-Briebe et al., 2023). The faunal assemblage contains 47,981 remains with an almost monospecific composition, overwhelmingly dominated by *Bison* sp. (98.4%, MNI=60) (Rodríguez-Hidalgo et al., 2017). These faunal remains are associated with a notable lithic assemblage comprising 10,735 artefacts, primarily exploitation products, with a lesser proportion of small retouched tools. As previously mentioned, chert is strikingly dominant in this assemblage, in contrast to the raw material composition observed in other Atapuerca assemblages (Figure 3). Technologically, the TD10.2-BB assemblage differs from the evolved Acheulean traditions documented in the underlying sublevels TD10.3 and TD10.4 (Mosquera et al., 2024). Instead, its composition more closely aligns with the overlying TD10.1 level, which has been characterised as an early Middle Palaeolithic industry (de Lombera-Hermida et al., 2020; Arteaga-Briebe, 2024).

Extensive taphonomic analyses demonstrate systematic butchery practices consistent with primary access to complete carcasses, followed by selective transport of high-yield elements (Rodríguez-Hidalgo, 2015; Rodríguez-Hidalgo et al., 2017). The anatomical representation, fracture patterns, anthropogenic marks, and differential transport patterns all support the interpretation of this sublevel as a bison kill-butcher site (Rodríguez-Hidalgo, 2015; Rodríguez-Hidalgo et al., 2017). Furthermore, the integration of seasonality data, archaeostratigraphic evidence, and lithic refitting patterns points to at least two short but intense bison hunting episodes (Rodríguez-Hidalgo et al., 2016; Arteaga-Briebe et al., 2023). The catastrophic mortality profiles, alongside the convergence of all other lines of evidence, strongly support the association of TD10.2-BB with mass communal hunting events around 400 ka (Rodríguez-Hidalgo et al., 2017; Rodríguez-Gómez et al., 2025), TD10.2-BB representing the earliest documented evidence of this complex cooperative behaviour in the human evolutionary record.

Such predation techniques would have required large-scale coordination, involving numerous individuals, with advanced planning and anticipatory capabilities (Driver,

1990; Steele and Baker, 1993; Driver and Maxwell, 2013). Within this framework, it can be hypothesised that each mass hunting event would have necessitated a substantial supply of lithic resources to process the large number of carcasses obtained. This demand would, in turn, have implied a high degree of logistical organisation in the procurement, transport, and management of lithic materials, potentially reflected in the composition of the assemblage.

Figure 3. a) General view of Gran Dolina during the excavation of TD10.2; b) Spatial distribution of the archaeological materials recovered from sublevel TD10.2-BB, showing faunal remains (grey) and lithic artefacts colour-coded by raw material, highlighting the clear predominance of chert (green); c-d) Detailed views illustrating the high density of bison remains documented during the excavation of TD10.2-BB; e) In situ detail of Cretaceous chert (left) and Neogene chert (right) artefacts. Photographs by Andreu Ollé (IPHES-CERCA).

To investigate this hypothesis and to better understand the predominance of chert in this assemblage, within the broader framework of subsistence strategies, this study draws upon previous specialised analyses of raw material characterisation and provenance in the Sierra de Atapuerca, specifically in TD10.2 (García-Antón, 2016a; 2016b; Soto et al., 2021). These data are complemented by a macroscopic identification of lithotypes across

the entire lithic assemblage, integrated into a comprehensive technological framework. This approach allows the management of raw materials to be contextualised within the site's behavioural dynamics, and the significance of chert selection in relation to the nature and organisation of the occupation events to be assessed.

2. RESULTS. Raw material management strategies at TD10.2-BB.

The lithic assemblage from TD10.2-BB comprises 10,735 artefacts with a clear predominance of flake products, which account for 68.26% of the total. These are followed by indeterminate items (24.58%), small retouched tools (3.38%), and a small proportion of cores and natural bases (unknapped materials in the form of manuports and hammerstones), which together represent less than 1% of the assemblage (Table 2).

The high proportion of indeterminate items stems from the severe post-depositional weathering of Neogene chert, which accounts for 98.6% of indeterminate elements, and frequently exhibits advanced chemical and mechanical damage. These alterations are mainly caused by the partial dissolution of the original silica matrix, sometimes leading to complete disintegration (Font et al., 2010; Ollé et al., 2013; Zornoza-Indart et al., 2017; 2021). As a result, diagnostic features are often obscured or entirely lost, rendering reliable technological attribution unfeasible.

When indeterminate items are excluded from the sample, flake products represent 94.26% of the assemblage, indicating intense knapping activity at the site and a pronounced emphasis on flake production. The metric data demonstrate a predominance of small-sized artefacts: 60.9% measure less than 20 mm in length, whereas only 0.89% exceed 60 mm (Figure 4). This size distribution indicates that reduction sequences were primarily directed towards the production of small blanks. The consistent presence of microflakes (13.9% < 10mm) reinforces this interpretation, providing strong evidence for *in situ* knapping activities. It also attests to the high degree of preservation and integrity of the deposit, as further supported by the presence of long refitting sequences (see below).

The assemblage is overwhelmingly dominated by chert, which accounts for 98.78% of all artefacts, other lithologies appearing only in marginal quantities (Figure 5).

Figure 4. Boxplot showing the distribution of artefact lengths (mm) by raw material type in TD10.2-BB. Black diamonds indicate mean values (μ), shown above each group.

Among the chert artefacts, 77.57% correspond to Neogene chert and 22.25% to Cretaceous chert. Despite its lower absolute frequency, the relative proportion of Cretaceous chert at TD10.2-BB is notably higher than that observed in most other contexts within the Atapuerca system (see Table 3). Among the Cretaceous lithotypes identified, RSV and VDC cherts occur in similar proportions, with only minor fluctuations across technological categories, as discussed below. In contrast, ARZ chert is scarcely represented, with just nine items documented.

Fluvial-derived detrital materials are likewise scarce. The assemblage includes 54 quartzite artefacts (0.5%), 44 sandstone elements (0.41%), and 24 quartz items (0.22%). Additionally, seven limestone implements and two slate fragments have been identified.

All raw materials recorded in TD10.2-BB originate from sources located less than 5 km from the site, many of them in the immediate vicinity of the cavity. The only exception is the ARZ chert, whose primary outcrop lies approximately 7 km away. Accordingly, raw material procurement strategies at TD10.2-BB can be described as strictly local, consistent with the pattern observed across all Pleistocene sites in the Atapuerca complex

(de Lombera-Hermida et al., 2015; 2020; García-Medrano et al., 2017; Mosquera et al., 2018; 2024).

Delving further into the distribution of technological categories by raw material (Table 2), some notable patterns emerge. Within flake production, chert clearly predominates. When indeterminate and fragmented items, which may otherwise obscure broader trends, are excluded, flake products represent 95.26% of the classifiable Neogene chert assemblage and 93.04% of the Cretaceous chert. Both formations also show almost identical proportions of cores (0.82% in Neogene and 0.85% in Cretaceous chert).

The most marked difference between the two chert varieties concerns the presence of retouched tools. Although Neogene chert dominates in absolute terms, retouched implements are relatively more frequent within the Cretaceous chert assemblage (6.05%) than within the Neogene (3.92%). This distinction becomes more pronounced when we focus specifically on small retouched tools: while Neogene chert still prevails numerically (57.85%), the proportion of Cretaceous chert within this category (38.29%) is noticeably higher than its overall presence in the assemblage. This relative overrepresentation suggests a deliberate preference for Cretaceous chert in the production of small retouched tools, probably linked to its superior workability (see Table 1).

Fluvial materials exhibit distinct technological patterns. Quartzite stands out for its frequent use for natural bases, which make up 16% of all quartzite items. Sandstone follows a similar pattern, with 13.79% of its artefacts also serving as natural bases. Limestone shows an even stronger association within this category, with 71.43% of artefacts identified as unmodified natural bases. Retouched tools also occur in similar proportions among quartzite (13.21%) and sandstone (13.64%), with quartz displaying a slightly higher incidence (16.67%), increasing to 19% when fragments are excluded from the count.

Overall, the raw material distribution at TD10.2-BB reflects a clear dichotomy in raw material management strategies. While all lithotypes are predominantly represented as flake products, cores are virtually absent among the fluvial materials. The only exception is a single quartzite core, which also functioned as a hammerstone and shows minimal exploitation. These fluvial materials tend to be associated with specific technical roles, particularly as natural bases, retouched tools, and small to medium-sized flakes (Figure 5).

TD10.2-BB	NB		Cores		Flake products		Retouched tools		Fragments		Indet.		Total	
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%
Neogene chert	-	-	44	0.53	5106	62.07	210	2.55	265	3.22	2601	31.62	8,226	76.63
Cretaceous chert	1	0.04	20	0.85	2138	90.59	139	5.89	48	2.03	14	0.59	2,360	21.98
RSV	-	-	10	1.42	628	88.95	54	7.65	13	1.84	1	0.14	706	29.92
VDC	1	0.12	8	0.87	724	90.05	54	6.72	17	2.11	-	-	804	34.07
ARZ	-	-	-	-	6	66.67	3	33.33	-	-	-	-	9	0.38
Indet. Chert	-	-	-	-	7	38.89	-	-	-	-	11	61.11	18	0.17
Quartzite	8	14.81	1	1.85	35	64.81	6	11.11	4	7.41	-	-	54	0.50
Sandstone	4	9.09	-	-	22	50.00	3	6.82	3	6.82	12	27.27	44	0.41
Quartz	-	-	-	-	17	70.83	4	16.67	3	12.5	-	-	24	0.22
Limestone	5	71.43	-	-	1	14.29	1	14.29	-	-	-	-	7	0.07
Slate	-	-	-	-	2	100	-	-	-	-	-	-	2	0.02
Total	18	0.17	65	0.61	7,328	68.26	363	3.38	323	3.01	2,638	24.57	10,735	100

Table 2. The TD10.2-BB lithic assemblage. Distribution by technological categories and raw materials. The percentage value in each row denotes the proportion of each category within the specific raw material group. The general percentages in the last column represent the proportion of each raw material relative to the entirety of the assemblage. Conversely, the total percentages in the last row reflect the frequency of each structural category within the TD10.2-BB lithic assemblage.

Beyond the quantitative distribution, the most informative aspects lie in the organisation of the *chaînes opératoires*. These are particularly supported by the analysis of lithic refitting. A total of 64 refit groups involving 191 artefacts have been identified, almost exclusively chert (Arteaga-Briebea, 2024). Of these, 23 groups (52 artefacts) correspond to Neogene chert, 39 groups (135 artefacts) to Cretaceous chert (including both VDC and RSV varieties), and only two groups (4 artefacts) to sandstone (Figure 6). No refits have been observed for quartzite or quartz.

Although a detailed technological characterisation of the assemblage and the refits is outside the scope of the present study, the results already point to significant differences in raw material management. Neogene chert was primarily introduced into the cavity in the form of fragments and large flakes, and subsequently subjected to *in situ* exploitation. Cretaceous chert (VDC and RSV varieties), generally introduced as small complete or fragmented nodules, also underwent *in situ* reduction, with refit groups documenting extended reduction sequences of up to 20 elements. The use of these materials includes not only blank exploitation from the initial stages of reduction, but also resharpening

events and the manufacture of small retouched tools, thereby indicating the occurrence of complete *chaînes opératoires* within the site.

Figure 5. Representative lithic materials from the TD10.2-BB assemblage. Percussive tools: (a) quartzite manuport; (b) sandstone manuport; (c) quartzite core with percussion marks. Chert cores: (d, e) Cretaceous RSV cores; (f, h) Neogene chert cores; (g) Cretaceous VDC core. Small tools: (i) Neogene convergent scraper; (j) Déjeté Cretaceous RSV scraper; (k) Cretaceous RSV denticulate scraper; (l) Cretaceous VDC point; (m) Cretaceous ARZ point; (n) quartz point; (o) quartzite end scraper and notch. Flakes: (p) Cretaceous RSV flake; (q) Cretaceous VDC cortical flake; (r) Cretaceous RSV flake; (s) Neogene flake; (t) Raw Material Unit in ARZ chert; (u) small-sized Cretaceous chert flakes. Photographs by María G. Guillén (IPHES-CERCA).

These strategies coexist, however, with the introduction of finished implements. This is particularly clear in the case of ARZ chert, which is only marginally present and lacks any lithic connection. Its presence as isolated flakes and retouched tools strongly suggests off-site production and subsequent transport to the cave.

In contrast, fluvial materials exhibit a higher fragmentation of the *chaînes opératoires*. They were primarily introduced to the site as unknapped pebbles or cobbles, finished tools, or small to medium-sized flakes, with no evidence of systematic reduction within the cave. The two refits identified in sandstone—one corresponding to a flake fracture and the other to an isolated edge resharpening—further support this pattern, pointing to the introduction of finished implements (Figure 6, d). Additionally, the presence of fluvial materials used as hammerstones suggests that these resources were selected and transported as functional complements to the chert toolkit, probably for specific percussion-related tasks.

3. DISCUSSION

Raw material procurement strategies across the Sierra de Atapuerca consistently reflect a strong reliance on locally available resources. Despite temporal and contextual variability, the same lithological resources, primarily Neogene and Cretaceous chert, quartzite, sandstone, quartz, and limestone, were systematically exploited by different hominin groups. The diversified use of local raw materials suggests a flexible approach to the geological landscape, whereby different hominin groups took advantage of the rich lithological spectrum surrounding the sites.

Within this broader pattern, the TD10.2-BB assemblage stands out as an exceptional case. With nearly 99% of the artefacts made of chert, this sublevel exhibits a markedly monospecific procurement strategy, sharply contrasting with the more diversified composition observed in other Atapuerca' assemblages, where fluvial components play a more prominent role (Table 3).

Comparable concentrations of chert are only documented in the open-air Upper Pleistocene sites that surround the Sierra (Navazo et al., 2008). For instance, Fuente Mudarra and Hotel California yield similar values to those reported in TD10.2-BB (see Table 3), although, in these cases, the predominance of chert is readily explained by the proximity of secondary Neogene chert outcrops (Santamaría et al., 2021; 2023).

Similarly, the Valle de las Orquídeas site presents very high frequencies of Cretaceous chert (Mosquera et al., 2007), a pattern likewise attributable to the site's location on top of a primary VDC outcrop.

In contrast, Middle Pleistocene deposits from within the Atapuerca karst system, where raw materials had to be deliberately transported into the caves, typically show more varied compositions. Although Neogene chert remains the most frequently found lithotype, owing to its greater abundance in the area, it rarely exceeds 60% of the assemblages. It is generally accompanied by a more diversified range of fluvial materials and Cretaceous chert, in variable proportions (see Table 3). A comparable degree of chert predominance is not observed until the Upper Pleistocene, in the Galería de las Estatuas assemblages, where it accounts for 83.34% of the total (Álvarez-Fernández et al., 2025). This high percentage has been interpreted as the outcome of a directed procurement strategy, probably involving logistical forays to specific source areas, which has been associated with an evolutionary trend towards increasingly selective provisioning behaviours among Neanderthal groups. Nevertheless, the authors caution that the small sample size limits the robustness of this interpretation (Álvarez-Fernández et al., 2025).

In this respect, the TD10.2-BB deposit does not appear to follow such a pattern. While elevated chert values are also observed in other sublevels of TD10.2 (see discussion below), this tendency does not persist in the immediately overlying TD10.1, where chert frequencies decrease. This discontinuity reinforces the interpretation of TD10.2-BB as a singular provisioning episode, marked by a highly focused strategy, rather than by a long-term trajectory in raw material selection. If the high chert frequencies observed in TD10.2-BB reflected an evolutionary shift towards more selective procurement behaviours, as has been proposed for Galería de las Estatuas, this pattern would be expected to persist, or even intensify, in the more recent TD10.1.

Crucially, TD10.1 and TD10.2-BB share most of their technological and compositional features, including similar techno-typological structures, retouched tool frequencies, and reduction strategies (de Lombera et al., 2020; Arteaga-Bribea et al., 2024). Given the marked technological continuity within the same stratigraphic sequence, the divergence in raw material representation becomes particularly significant. Explanations grounded in cultural traditions or technological requirements are, therefore, difficult to sustain. Instead, the pronounced difference in raw material representation more plausibly reflects a specific provisioning choice rather than a technological shift.

Site and archaeological layer	Chrono.	Neo.ch	Cret.ch	Ind. ch.	Total ch.	Quartzite	Sandstone	Quartz	Limestone	Total artefacts	
TD10	Up.TD10.A	Late MP	54.46	4.8	6.17	65.43	21.54	10.84	1.37	0.82	729
	Up.TD10.B	Late MP	52.17	4.35	7.25	63.77	20.29	13.04	0.72	<1	138
	Low.TD10.1	Late MP	51.3	6.66	2.96	60.92	17.24	18.2	3.44	0.11	21,522
	Up. TD10.2	Mid MP	74.19	15.86	0.72	90.77	4.81	2.93	1.11	0.33	1,538
	TD10.2-BB	Mid MP	76.63	21.98	0.17	98.78	0.5	0.41	0.22	0.07	10,735
	TD10.2.2	Mid MP	68.78	14.98	1.27	85.03	9.07	3.80	0.42	1.69	474
	TD10.3-Sup	Mid MP	60.2	12.1	1.9	74.2	12.1	9	1.8	2.5	666
	TD10.3-Inf	Mid MP	39.3	3.1	0.7	43.1	37.5	9	4.2	6.1	570
TD10.4	Mid MP	61.1	8.1	1.2	70.4	20.2	6.5	2.8	-	247	
TD6	TD6.1	Late EP	51.61	16.13	0.81	68.55	16.13	7.26	4.84	3.23	124
	TD6.2.0/1	Late EP	36.19	15.24	1.43	52.86	24.29	8.57	6.19	8.10	210
	TD6.2.2/3	Late EP	34.79	14.69	0.77	50.25	22.94	10.82	9.28	6.70	388
	TD6.2.4	Late EP	37.71	5.08	0.85	43.64	23.73	12.71	6.78	13.14	236
	Up.TD6.3	Late EP	3.51	3.51	21.05	28.07	21.05	21.05	14.04	15.79	56
	Low.TD6.3	Late EP	17.86	3.57	-	21.43	42.86	7.14	3.57	21.43	28
TE	TE19	Late MP	25	5.6	8.3	38.9	33.3	27.8	-	-	36
	TE9	EP	33.68	7.37	11.58	52.63	-	-	2.11	45.26	95
Galería	GIIIb	Late MP	37.5	4.55	1.14	43.19	31.82	17.05	2.27	4.17	264
	GIIIa	Late MP	46.75	3.90	0.65	51.3	28.90	13.31	4.55	1.95	308
	GIIb	Mid MP	51.92	8.41	0.24	60.57	18.51	9.62	3.61	7.21	416
	GIIa	MP	49.82	6.5	-	56.32	33.57	8.3	0.72	1.08	277
GE	-	Mid UP	71.8	11.54	-	83.34	13.98	1.63	0.81	0.16	615
V.O	-	Up. Pal	0.6	87.2	-	87.8	10.4	0.3	0.3	1	306
Hotel California	L3	Up. Pal	95.36	2.64	-	98	1.54	0.44	-	-	453
	L4	Up. Pal	93.82	3.93	-	97.75	0.56	1.12	0.56	-	178
	L5	Up. Pal	96.01	1.99	-	98	1.49	0.49	-	-	202
	L6	Up. Pal	93.19	5.44	-	98.63	0.68	0.68	-	-	294
	L7	Up. Pal	86.47	10.37	-	96.84	3.14	-	-	-	318
F.Mударra	L4	Up. Pal	89.31	1.64	2.36	93.31	3.52	-	2.36	-	1394
	L5	Up. Pal	91.24	6.06	0.33	97.63	1.01	-	0.67	-	297
	L7	Up. Pal	71.51	1.02	16.32	88.85	6.12	-	1.02	-	98
	L8	Up. Pal	81.33	1.43	0.95	83.71	11.96	-	1.43	-	209

Table 3. Distribution of raw materials in the main representative archaeological deposits of Sierra de Atapuerca (Gran Dolina, Sima del Elefante, Galería, Galería de las Estatuas, Valle de las Orquídeas, Hotel California y Fuente Mudarra). The table includes archaeological layers with the largest number of lithic artefacts (Mosquera et al., 2007; 2018; 2024; de Lombera-Hermida et al., 2015; 2020; García-Medrano et al., 2015; Santamaría et al., 2021; 2023; Arteaga-Briebea, 2024; Álvarez-Fernández et al., 2025). Abbreviations: Neo.ch. = Neogene chert; Cret.ch. = Cretaceous chert; Ind.ch. =

indeterminate chert; Up. = Upper; Low. = Lower; Sup. = Superior; Inf. = Inferior; MP = Middle Pleistocene; EP = Early Pleistocene; UP = Upper Palaeolithic.

One would expect differences in raw material procurement between sites to reflect factors such as availability, distance, or the suitability for knapping of the resources present in the landscape (see above). However, the TD10.2-BB assemblage does not conform neatly to these explanatory models. If procurement strategies were primarily conditioned by geological or environmental constraints, we would anticipate similar patterns across the Atapuerca sites, given that they all share the same lithological setting. The singular character of the TD10.2-BB assemblage calls for a critical reassessment of the key variables traditionally considered as explaining raw material selection.

Regarding distance, all raw materials recorded at the subunit are local. Some varieties, like the RSV Cretaceous chert or the limestones, are located in the immediate vicinity of Gran Dolina. Furthermore, these resources are readily accessible and available, especially the Neogene chert and quartzites, although the occurrence of Cretaceous chert is more limited (García-Antón, 2016a). Given the availability of such a broad range of materials, it is unlikely that distance alone can account for the strong preference for chert.

In terms of size, Neogene chert poses no limitations, mirroring the versatility of quartzites and sandstones, which occur in a wide range of shapes and dimensions (García-Antón, 2016a). Cretaceous chert varieties tend to be smaller, with VDC nodules rarely exceeding 10 cm (García-Antón, 2016a, p. 89). Nevertheless, size does not appear to have constrained the TD10.2-BB assemblage, which is characterised by the predominance of small-sized artefacts (Figure 4). The prevalence of small metrics could be interpreted as a strategy to maximise the use of raw materials under conditions of scarcity. However, this rationale is not applicable to the Atapuerca context, where lithic resources are both abundant and diverse.

The morphological attributes of the different raw materials shed light on their selection for specific uses. Quartzite, sandstone, and limestone pebbles and cobbles generally exhibit spherical or sub-spherical shapes, with a mass that makes them particularly suitable for percussive tasks and ideal as blanks for the production of large cutting tools, which require sizeable materials. This is particularly clear in the case of flat-shaped sandstone cobbles, highly suitable for handaxe production (Terradillos-Bernal and Rodríguez-Álvarez, 2017).

These attributes help explain why fluvial-derived raw materials (especially quartzite and sandstone) are more abundant in TD10.4 and TD10.3 and in the adjacent site of Galería, where large cutting tools and hammerstones occur at substantially higher frequencies than in TD10.2-BB (García-Medrano et al., 2014; 2015; Mosquera et al., 2024). In TD10.2-BB, by contrast, LCTs are nearly absent and hammerstone are scarce (see Table 2).

Figure 6. Selected refits from TD10.2-BB. (a) Reduction sequence in Neogene chert; (b) reduction sequences in Cretaceous chert, above in RSV-type chert and below in VDC-type chert; (c) conjoin in Neogene chert; (d) the only sandstone refit identified in the assemblage, documenting a resharpening sequence. Photographs by María G. Guillén (IPHES-CERCA).

Although morpho-functional considerations help account for the reduced presence of fluvial materials in the sublevel, they are insufficient to explain their virtual absence throughout the remaining stages of the lithic reduction sequence. In TD10.3–4 and in the different units of Galería, fluvial raw materials are well represented and occur across all technological categories. Moreover, they are not generally associated with the on-site production of large cutting tools, as refitting analyses indicate that many LCTs entered these sites already partially or fully shaped (Mosquera et al., 2024; García-Medrano et al., 2017). The marked scarcity of fluvial materials in TD10.2-BB therefore points to factors beyond raw material morphology and functional demands.

Regarding raw material quality, Cretaceous chert, particularly the VDC variety, is recognised for its finer grain and medium-to-high knapping quality. This chert type yields highly effective and durable edges, although it requires greater force during tool production (Terradillos-Bernal and Rodríguez-Álvarez, 2014). Nevertheless, this

material occasionally displays irregularities and internal fissures that can lead to unpredictable fractures.

The superior knappability of Cretaceous chert provides a functional rationale for its preferred use in the production of formal tools (Mallol, 1999; Mosquera et al., 2018; de Lomberra-Hermida et al., 2020). The preference for Cretaceous chert over Neogene varieties in the manufacture of small shaped implements at TD10.2-BB can thus be understood as a deliberate selection strategy grounded in its qualitative advantages.

However, Terradillos-Bernal and Rodríguez-Álvarez (2014, p. 540) offer an alternative perspective, proposing that the consistent use of Cretaceous chert in TD6, which also shows a high proportion of this chert (see Table 3) and TD10 may be rooted in cultural traditions. From this point of view, given the availability of abundant Neogene chert of medium-to-high quality and no size limitations, the increased effort involved in locating Cretaceous chert may not be fully explainable by purely utilitarian advantages.

Ongoing experimental programmes aimed at quantifying edge durability and mechanical resistance are expected to refine these qualitative assessments, contributing to a more empirically grounded understanding of the functional properties and behavioural implications of raw material selection in Atapuerca.

Neogene chert is characterised by good workability, although it is heterogeneous and presents considerable internal variability (Ollé et al., 2013). Its low resistance to conchoidal fracturing facilitates the detachment of numerous flakes from relatively narrow platforms, rendering it more productive than fluvial materials (Terradillos-Bernal and Rodríguez-Álvarez, 2014). Furthermore, the supply of Neogene chert in the form of large flakes or non-cortical fragments provides advantageous initial volumes and suitable angles that significantly reduce investment in initial processing.

Quartzite and sandstone from the Arlanzón terraces exhibit moderate knapping quality, but with high variability influenced by grain size and internal fissures. Experimental studies have demonstrated that these materials are easier to shape than Cretaceous chert, but the resulting edges tend to be duller and less regular (Terradillos-Bernal and Rodríguez-Álvarez, 2014). Lastly, quartz displays moderate to low suitability for knapping, as it does not consistently fracture conchoidally. Its lower abundance and its occurrence in smaller formats account for its limited representation within the archaeological assemblages (Ollé et al., 2013).

In summary, the exclusive preference for chert in TD10.2 reflects a complex scenario that goes beyond geological or geographical determinants. While the broad availability of Neogene chert explains its frequent presence in the assemblage, it does not account for the near absence of fluvial materials. Nor does it explain the high proportion of Cretaceous chert, which is less abundant and less visible in the landscape, as it often involves the disintegration of the limestone pavement.

Similarly, although the physical and mechanical properties of raw material may explain certain trends, such as the scarcity of quartz or the widespread use of Neogene chert, these attributes alone do not fully account for the almost complete absence of quartzite and sandstone in TD10.2-BB.

From a cost-benefit perspective, it can be argued that the high productivity of Neogene chert and its ability to produce sharp and durable edges is particularly advantageous in a context where butchery is a key occupation, such as TD10.2-BB. This characteristic of Neogene chert would make it a more efficient choice than other materials. However, considering the abundant availability of lithic resources in the area, it is unlikely that prioritising material efficiency alone dictated procurement strategies. The almost exclusive choice of chert, despite the availability of other suitable materials, suggests selection criteria that extend beyond geographical proximity and physical properties.

What is clearly evidenced by the archaeological record is that the preference for chert indicates a shift in resource-gathering areas, moving from fluvial terrace environments and secondary deposits to the exploitation of primary and sub-primary chert formations, located in the higher areas and slopes of the Atapuerca ridge (Figure 1). This shift denotes a reconfiguration in the spatial logic of raw material procurement and prompts questions about the underlying reasons for this change in landscape use. Building on this evidence, we hypothesise that this transition may be linked to the bison hunting activities documented in TD10.2-BB and propose a correlation between subsistence strategies and lithic resource selection.

The communal hunting model posited for TD10.2-BB suggests that bison herds were driven towards the Gran Dolina cavity, which functioned as a natural trap (Rodríguez-Hidalgo, 2015; 2016; Rodríguez-Hidalgo et al., 2017). While the specific hunting techniques remain unknown, it is reasonable to assume that bison were intercepted in the upper parts and slopes of the Atapuerca ridge rather than in the fluvial terraces. This inference is supported by the logistical impracticality of dragging at least 60 complete

bison carcasses uphill to Gran Dolina from the fluvial terraces, a highly unlikely and energetically inefficient endeavour. Consequently, the most efficient scenario is that bison were present in the upper areas at the time of the hunt, potentially implying that, during the occupations of TD10.2-BB, human groups primarily operated in areas where bison grazed and where chert was readily available. Accordingly, the chert specialisation observed in TD10.2-BB may reflect an embedded procurement strategy, intrinsically linked to bison hunting activities.

In line with this hypothesis, raw material procurement would presumably occur either immediately before or concurrently during the processing of bison carcasses, depending on the success of the hunt, the number of carcasses obtained, and the volume of artefacts required for butchery and related tasks. In this context, the notion of an “embedded strategy” does not strictly refer to the acquisition of raw materials during the performance of other subsistence tasks (as originally defined by Binford, 1979), but rather to a pattern in which procurement is contingent upon the acquisition of prey. This strategy may have involved direct trips to nearby chert sources, yet always within the spatial landscape shaped by the main hunting activity. In this regard, we concur with other authors who contend that the dichotomy between embedded and direct procurement is overly rigid and reductive (McCall, 2012; Shimelmitz et al., 2020; Agam and Finkel, 2024). As Mears and Wilson (2023) point out, these concepts would be better understood as two ends of a behavioural continuum, along which prehistoric groups could have shifted, depending on situational demands.

This proposed model suggests planned procurement behaviour at TD10.2-BB, within an environment known for its abundant abiotic resources. Rather than resulting from opportunistic behaviours, where assemblage composition would reflect the relative abundance of raw materials in the vicinity (Brantingham, 2003; Raichlen et al., 2014), the evidence points towards deliberate selection. Therefore, the procurement model is both generalist, as it aligns with the natural occurrence of different chert lithotypes, and specialised, with a preference for higher quality materials for tool production.

In this scenario, the hunter-gatherer group at TD10.2-BB appear to have arrived with part of their toolkit already prepared, including percussive implements, large flakes, and small, often curated tools, made from high-quality materials (particularly VDC and ARZ Cretaceous chert). This toolkit was then supplemented by local procurement and immediate in situ flake production and tool-making during butchery activity, reflecting

an adaptive strategy grounded in foresight and situational flexibility (Arteaga-Briebea, 2024).

The communal hunting model proposed for TD10.2-BB (Rodríguez-Hidalgo et al., 2017) additionally alludes to a cooperative hunting strategy involving a high level of coordination and a significant number of participants (Driver, 1990; 1995). This model potentially encompasses individuals not typically engaged in hunting activities (Speth, 2013), suggesting a kind of division of labour within the group. These individuals could have acted as beaters, helping to drive or track bison (Forbis, 1978), or have provided support in other tasks such as raw material procurement for subsequent carcass processing.

In response to this interpretation, it might be pointed out that both TD10.2.2 and Upper TD10.2 show a significant presence of chert, despite neither being identified as a kill-butchered site with communal hunting. However, it is important to bear in mind that the much larger size and prominence of the TD10.2-BB assemblage may affect the archaeological record. Despite efforts to accurately differentiate the sublevels (Arteaga-Briebea et al., 2023), some degree of residual mixing or overlap with TD10.2-BB deposit may persist. This potential influence could partly explain the relatively high presence of chert in both sublevels, even though they display different chaînes opératoires and a greater proportion of fluvial-derived materials. Moreover, the consistent preference for chert across the three sublevels might reflect a persistent cultural or practical predilection for this material, arising from factors that remain difficult to discern given the current evidence.

Finally, the homogeneity of chert resources in TD10.2-BB provides valuable insights into the site's temporal framework and occupational dynamics. Two significant implications emerge from this uniformity. First, the recurrent use of chert across successive bison hunting events implies a continuity in raw material procurement strategies, potentially reflecting repeated visits by the same group within short intervals or the persistence of shared technological knowledge transmitted over time. Second, the very low raw material diversity in TD10.2-BB probably implies a limited number of brief hunting events, as more prolonged or overlapping occupations over time would result in a more varied assemblage. Taken together, these observations reinforce the archaeostratigraphic evidence, which points to a small number of short, discrete hunting events at the site (Arteaga-Briebea et al., 2023).

4. CONCLUSIONS

TD10.2-BB provides an exceptional window into the behavioural complexity underlying raw material procurement strategies. Its analytical potential derives from the unique combination of a nearly monospecific chert assemblage, high temporal resolution, a well-constrained functional context, and a well-characterised lithological setting. Embedded within one of the most continuous Pleistocene occupation sequences in Europe, this sublevel enables procurement strategies to be examined diachronically under stable geographical and geological conditions.

The TD10.2-BB assemblage documents a marked shift in raw material procurement patterns, with no parallel in any other subunit of the Gran Dolina sequence or in nearby Pleistocene sites at Atapuerca. Apart from this compositional distinctiveness, TD10.2-BB also provides evidence for a reconfiguration of landscape management and mobility strategies, reflected in changes in procurement areas from fluvial terraces to the slopes and upper parts of the ridge. This pattern highlights the potential for identifying variations in landscape use even at a highly localised level within the Atapuerca system.

We have reassessed the main factors traditionally invoked to explain raw material selection, highlighting the limitations of explanatory frameworks based on isolated variables or deterministic assumptions. The specific behaviours observed at TD10.2-BB, particularly when considered within the broader comparative context of the Atapuerca Pleistocene sites, indicate that procurement strategies cannot be fully accounted for by geographical proximity, the availability of raw materials, or physical properties alone. Instead, they should be interpreted within an integrated behavioural framework that incorporates technological, functional, and contextual dimensions.

Building on this reconsideration, we propose an explanatory model linking the provisioning strategies observed at TD10.2-BB with the specific activities carried out at the site. A key insight emerging from this study is the importance of site functionality, an often underexplored dimension in discussions of provisioning strategies. In the case of TD10.2-BB, the site was recurrently used as a kill-butchered area in the context of mass communal hunting practices. This subsistence behaviour presupposes advanced planning and logistical organisation, constrained mobility linked to predictable faunal resources, and the participation of large structured groups. It is reasonable to hypothesise that these conditions imposed specific technological requirements and procurement strategies,

organised around the contingencies of hunting success and the demands of carcass processing. The recurrence of this behavioural pattern throughout successive hunting events is further evidence for the continuity of these procurement strategies, provided that the site maintains the same role, pointing to a supply model grounded in anticipatory planning, yet characterised by significant behavioural plasticity.

We acknowledge that this explanatory model remains necessarily inferential, as any attempt to interpret raw material selection ultimately involves an approximation to hominin intentionality, an inherently inaccessible domain when approached through archaeological proxies. Without direct evidence, such interpretations must rely on theoretical constructs informed by technological, spatial, and contextual analyses.

Ultimately, the case of TD10.2-BB underscores the analytical potential of long-term diachronic sequences, such as those found at Atapuerca. It also highlights the importance of drawing together multiple lines of evidence in order to fully grasp the complexity of hominin behaviour. It is only through such multi-scalar, interdisciplinary approaches that we can begin to reconstruct the decision-making processes that underlie raw material selection in the Pleistocene archaeological record.

Acknowledgements

We would like to thank the Atapuerca Research Team for their continued support and dedication, which make this project possible year after year. We are also grateful to M. Soto for her insightful explanations regarding the formation of Neogene chert, and to A. Rodríguez-Hidalgo and P. Saladié for their always enriching discussions on the TD10.2-BB assemblage.

Funding

This study was funded by the Spanish Ministry of Science, Innovation and Universities (PID2024-156477NB-C31 funded by MICIU/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and by FEDER, EU), the Agency for the Management of University and Research Grants of the Generalitat de Catalunya (SGR2021-01239), and the Universitat Rovira i Virgili (2023PFR-URV-01239). The IPHES-CERCA has received financial support through the “María de Maeztu” program for Units of Excellence (CEX2024-01485-M), funded by MICIU/AEI/10.13039/501100011033. A. Arteaga-Brieba is supported by the DEATHREVOL project (Grant Agreement No. 949330) that has received funding from

the European Research Council under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program. Fieldwork at Atapuerca is supported by Junta de Castilla y León and the Fundación Atapuerca.

References

Abrunhosa, A., Pereira, T., Márquez, B., Baquedano, E., Arsuaga, J.L., Pérez-González, A., 2019. Understanding Neanderthal technological adaptation at Navalmaíllo Rock Shelter (Spain) by measuring lithic raw materials performance variability. *Archaeological and Anthropological Sciences* 11, 5949–5962. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12520-019-00826-3>

Agam, A., 2020. Late lower paleolithic lithic procurement and exploitation strategies: A view from Acheulo-Yabrudian Qesem Cave (Israel). *Journal of Archaeological Science: Reports* 33, 102447. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jasrep.2020.102447>

Agam, A., Finkel, M., 2024. Re-thinking the concept of embedded procurement: Insights from the lower Paleolithic of the Levant. *Journal of Archaeological Science: Reports* 60. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jasrep.2024.104824>

Álvarez-Fernández, A., Casado, A.I., Aranburu, A., Damas-Mollá, L., Rodríguez, L., Márquez, B., Arsuaga, J.L., García-González, R., 2025. New and old approaches to understand lithic raw materials: The case of Galería de las Estatuas site (Sierra de Atapuerca, Spain). *Journal of Archaeological Science: Reports* 62, 105044. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jasrep.2025.105044>

Andrefsky, W., 1994. Raw-Material Availability and the Organization of Technology. *American Antiquity* 59, 21–34. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3085499>

Andrefsky, W., 2008. Projectile point provisioning strategies and human land-use. In: Andrefsky, W. (Ed.), *Lithic Technology: Measures of Production, Use and Curation*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, pp. 195–216.

Arsuaga, J.L., Gómez-Olivencia, A., Sala, N., Martínez-Pillado, V., Pablos, A., Bonmatí, A., Pantoja-Pérez, A., Lira-Garrido, J., Alcázar de Velasco, A., Ortega, A.I., Cuenca-Bescós, G., García, N., Aranburu, A., Ruiz-Zapata, B., Gil-García, M.J., Rodríguez-Álvarez, X.P., Ollé, A., Mosquera, M., 2017. Evidence of paleoecological changes and

Mousterian occupations at the Galería de las Estatuas site, Sierra de Atapuerca, northern Iberian plateau, Spain. *Quaternary Research* 88, 345–367. <https://doi.org/10.1017/qua.2017.46>

Arteaga-Briebea, A., 2024. Among stones and bison. The lithic assemblage of Gran Dolina TD10.2 (Atapuerca). Technological and spatial implications of a specialised Middle Pleistocene Kill-butchered site. *Universitat Rovira i Virgili*.

Arteaga-Briebea, A., Courtenay, L.A., Cobo-Sánchez, L., Rodríguez-Hidalgo, A., Saladié, P., Ollé, A., Mosquera, M., 2023. An archaeostratigraphic consideration of the Gran Dolina TD10.2 cultural sequence from a quantitative approach. *Quaternary Science Reviews* 309. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quascirev.2023.108033>

Asryan, L., Ollé, A., Moloney, N., King, T., 2014. Lithic assemblages of Azokh Cave (Nagorno Karabagh, Lesser Caucasus): Raw materials, technology and regional context. *Journal of Lithic Studies* 1, 33–54. <https://doi.org/10.2218/jls.v1i1.775>

Assaf, E., 2018. Paleolithic aesthetics: Collecting colorful flint pebbles at Middle Pleistocene Qesem Cave, Israel. *Journal of Lithic Studies* 5, 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.2218/jls.2616>

Ataman, K., Carambelas, K.R., Elston, R.G., 1992. The economics of toolstone extraction and processing. In: Elston, R.G., Raven, C. (Eds.), *Archaeological Investigations at Tosawih, a Great Basin Quarry, Part 3: A Perspective from Locality 36*. Nevada Bureau of Land Management Cultural Resource Series 16(10), pp. 230–250.

Bailey, G., 2007. Time perspectives, palimpsests and the archaeology of time. *Journal of Anthropological Archaeology* 26, 198–223. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaa.2006.08.002>

Bamforth, D.B., 1986. Technological Efficiency and Tool Curation. *American Antiquity* 51, 38–50.

Beck, C., Taylor, A.K., Jones, G.T., Fadem, C.M., Cook, C.R., Millward, S.A., 2002. Rocks are heavy: transport costs and Paleoarchaic quarry behavior in the Great Basin. *Journal of Anthropological Archaeology* 21, 481–507.

Benito-Calvo, A., 2004. Análisis geomorfológico y reconstrucción de paleopaisajes neógenos y cuaternarios en la Sierra de Atapuerca y el valle medio del río Arlanzón. *Universidad Complutense de Madrid*.

- Benito-Calvo, A., Pérez-González, A., 2007. Erosion surfaces and Neogene landscape evolution in the NE Duero Basin (north-central Spain). *Geomorphology* 88, 226–241. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geomorph.2006.11.005>
- Benito-Calvo, A., Pérez-González, A., 2015. Geomorphology of the Sierra de Atapuerca and the Middle Arlanzón Valley (Burgos, Spain). *Journal of Maps* 11(4), 535–544. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17445647.2014.909339>
- Benito-Calvo, A., Ortega, A.I., Pérez-González, A., Campaña, I., Bermúdez de Castro, J.M., Carbonell, E., 2017. Palaeogeographical reconstruction of the Sierra de Atapuerca Pleistocene sites (Burgos, Spain). *Quaternary International* 433, Part A, 379–392. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quaint.2015.10.034>
- Benito-Calvo, A., Ortega, A.I., Navazo, M., Moreno, D., Pérez-González, A., Parés, J.M., Bermúdez De Castro, J.M., Carbonell, E., 2018. Pleistocene geodynamic evolution of the Arlanzón valley: Implications for the formation of the endokarst system and the open air archaeological sites of the Sierra de Atapuerca (Burgos, España). *Boletín Geológico y Minero* 129, 59–82. <https://doi.org/10.21701/bolgeomin.129.1.003>
- Berger, G.W., Pérez-González, A., Carbonell, E., Arsuaga, J.L., Bermúdez de Castro, J.M., Ku, T.L., 2008. Luminescence chronology of cave sediments at the Atapuerca paleoanthropological site, Spain. *Journal of Human Evolution* 55, 300–311. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhevol.2008.02.012>
- Binford, L.R., 1979. Organization and Formation Processes: Looking at Curated Technologies. *Journal of Anthropological Research* 35, 255–273.
- Bird, D.W., O’Connell, J.F., 2006. Behavioral ecology and archaeology. *Journal of Archaeological Research* 14, 143–188. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10814-006-9003-6>
- Bleed, P., 1986. The Optimal Design of Hunting Weapons Maintainability or Reliability. *American Antiquity* 51, 737–747.
- Brantingham, P.J., 2003. A Neutral Model of Stone Raw Material Procurement. *American Antiquity* 68, 487–509. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3557105>
- Brantingham, P.J., Olsen, J.W., Rech, J.A., Krivoshapkin, A.I., 2000. Raw material quality and prepared core technologies in Northeast Asia. *Journal of Archaeological Science* 27, 255–271. <https://doi.org/10.1006/jasc.1999.0456>

Braun, D.R., Plummer, T., Ferraro, J. V., Ditchfield, P., Bishop, L.C., 2009. Raw material quality and Oldowan hominin toolstone preferences: evidence from Kanjera South, Kenya. *Journal of Archaeological Science* 36, 1605–1614. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jas.2009.03.025>

Browne, C.L., Wilson, L., 2011. Resource selection of lithic raw materials in the Middle Palaeolithic in southern France. *Journal of Human Evolution* 61, 597–608. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhevol.2011.08.004>

Campaña, I., Benito-Calvo, A., Pérez-González, A., Ortega, A.I., Bermúdez de Castro, J.M., Carbonell, E., 2017. Pleistocene sedimentary facies of the Gran Dolina archaeo-paleoanthropological site (Sierra de Atapuerca, Burgos, Spain). *Quat. Int.* 433, 68-84. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quaint.2015.04.023>. Carbonell, E., García-Antón, M.D., Mallol, C., Mosquera, M., Ollé, A., Rodríguez, X.P., Sahnouni, M., Sala, R., Vergès, J.M., 1999. The TD6 level lithic industry from Gran Dolina, Atapuerca (Burgos, Spain): production and use. *Journal of Human Evolution* 37, 653–693. <https://doi.org/10.1006/jhev.1999.0336>

Carbonell, E., Bermúdez de Castro, J.M., Parés, J.M., Pérez-González, A., Cuenca-Bescós, G., Ollé, A., Mosquera, M., Huguet, R., Van der Made, J., Rosas, A., Sala, R., Vallverdú, J., García, N., Granger, D.E., Martínón-Torres, M., Rodríguez, X.P., Stock, G.M., Vergès, J.M., Allué, E., Burjachs, F., Cáceres, I., Canals, A., Benito, A., Díez, C., Lozano, M., Mateos, A., Navazo, M., Rodríguez, J., Rosell, J., Arsuaga, J.L., 2008. The first hominin of Europe. *Nature* 452, 465–469. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature06815>

Carbonell, E., Huguet, R., Cáceres, I., Lorenzo, C., Mosquera, M., Ollé, A., Rodríguez-Álvarez, X.-P., Saladié, P., Vergès, J.M., García-Medrano, P., Rosell, J., Vallverdú, J., Carretero, J.M., Navazo, M., Ortega, A.I., Martínón-Torres, M., Morales, J.I., Allué, E., Aramburu, A., Canals, A., Carrancho, Á., Castilla, M., Expósito, I., Fontanals, M., Francés, M., Galindo-Pellicena, M.Á., García-Antón, M.D., García, N., Gracia, A., García, R., Gómez-Merino, G., Iriarte, E., de Lombra-Hermida, A., López-Polín, L., Lozano, M., Van der Made, J., Martínez, I., Mateos, A., Pérez-Romero, A., Poza-Rey, E., Quam, R., Rodríguez-Hidalgo, A., Rodríguez, J., Rodríguez, I., Santos, E., Terradillos, M., Bermúdez de Castro, J.M., Arsuaga, J.-L., 2014. Sierra de Atapuerca archaeological sites. In: Sala-Ramos, R., Carbonell, E., Bermúdez de Castro, J.M., Arsuaga, J. L. (Eds.),

Pleistocene and Holocen Hunter-Gatherers in Iberia and the Gibraltar Strait: The Current Archaeological Record. *Fundación Atapuerca*, pp. 534–560.

Clark, J., Linares-Matás, G., 2021. The Role of Landscape Knowledge Networks in the Early Pleistocene Technological Variability of East Africa. *Archaeological Review from Cambridge* 35, 25–44. <https://doi.org/10.17863/CAM.71847>

Conneller, C., 2012. *An archaeology of Materials. Substantial transformations in Early Prehistoric Europe*. Routledge.

de Lombera-Hermida, A., Rodríguez, X.-P., Fábregas, R., Moncel, M.-H., 2011. Quartz management during the Middle and Upper Pleistocene. Three case studies from southern Europe. *L'Anthropologie* 115, 294–331. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anthro.2011.02.003>

de Lombera-Hermida, A., Bargalló, A., Terradillos-Bernal, M., Huguet, R., Vallverdú, J., García-Antón, M.D., Mosquera, M., Ollé, A., Sala, R., Carbonell, E., Rodríguez-Álvarez, X.P., 2015. The lithic industry of Sima del Elefante (Atapuerca, Burgos, Spain) in the context of Early and Middle Pleistocene technology in Europe. *Journal of Human Evolution* 82, 95–106. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhevol.2015.03.002>

de Lombera-Hermida, A., Rodríguez-Álvarez, X.P., Mosquera, M., Ollé, A., García-Medrano, P., Pedergnana, A., Terradillos-Bernal, M., López-Ortega, E., Bargalló, A., Rodríguez-Hidalgo, A., Saladié, P., Bermúdez de Castro, J.M., Carbonell, E., 2020. The dawn of the Middle Paleolithic in Atapuerca: the lithic assemblage of TD10.1 from Gran Dolina. *Journal of Human Evolution* 145. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhevol.2020.102812>

Dibble, H.L., 1991. Local Raw Material Exploitation and its Effects on Lower and Middle Paleolithic Assemblage Variability. In **Montet-White A. & Holen S. (Eds.), *Raw material economies among prehistoric hunter-gatherers*, pp. 34-47. University of Kansas, *Publications in Anthropology* 19.**

Ditchfield, K., 2016. The influence of raw material size on stone artefact assemblage formation: An example from Bone Cave, south-western Tasmania. *Quaternary International* 422, 29–43. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quaint.2016.03.013>

Driver, J.C., 1990. Meat in due season: the timing of communal hunts. In: Davies, L.B., Reeves, B.O.K. (Eds.), *Hunters of the Recent Past*. Routledge, London, pp. 11–33.

Duval, M., Arnold, L.J., Demuro, M., Parés, J.M., Campaña, I., Carbonell, E., Bermúdez de Castro, J.M., 2022. New chronological constraints for the lowermost stratigraphic unit of Atapuerca Gran Dolina (Burgos, N Spain). *Quat. Geochronol.* 71, 101292. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quageo.2022.101292>. Driver, J.C., 1995. Social hunting and multiple predation. *MASCA Research Papers in Science and Archaeology* 12, 23–38.

Driver, J.C., Maxwell, D., 2013. Bison death assemblages and the interpretation of human hunting behaviour. *Quaternary International* 297, 100–109. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quaint.2012.12.038>

Elston, R.G., 1994. Economics and Strategies of Lithic Production at Tosawihi. In: Elston, R.G., Raven, C. (Eds.), *Archaeological Investigations at Tosawihi, A Great Basin Quarry, Part 1: The Periphery*. Inter-mountain Research and Bureau of Land Management, Silver City, Nevada, pp. 775–801.

Eren, M.I., Lycett, S.J., Roos, C.I., Sampson, C.G., 2011. Toolstone constraints on knapping skill: Levallois reduction with two different raw materials. *Journal of Archaeological Science* 38, 2731–2739. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jas.2011.06.011>

Eren, M.I., Roos, C.I., Story, B.A., Cramon-Taubadel, N. von, Lycett, S.J., 2014. The role of raw material differences in stone tool shape variation: An experimental assessment. *Journal of Archaeological Science* 49, 472–487. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jas.2014.05.034>

Falguères, C., Bahain, J.-J., Yokoyama, Y., Arsuaga, J.L., Bermúdez De Castro, J.M., Carbonell, E., Bischoff, J.L., Dolo, J.M., 1999. Earliest humans in Europe: The age of TD6 Gran Dolina, Atapuerca, Spain. *Journal of Human Evolution* 37, 343–352. <https://doi.org/10.1006/jhev.1999.0326>

Falguères, C., Bahain, J.-J., Yokoyama, Y., Bischoff, J.L., Arsuaga, J.L., Bermúdez de Castro, J.M., Carbonell, E., Dolo, J.M., 2001. Datation par RPE et U-TH des sites pléistocènes d'Atapuerca: Sima de los Huesos, Trinchera Dolina et Trinchera Galería. Bilan géochronologique. *L'Anthropologie* 105, 71–81. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0003-5521\(01\)80006-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0003-5521(01)80006-6)

Findlow, F.J., Bolognese, M., 1982. Regional modeling of obsidian procurement in the American Southwest. In: Ericson, J.E., Earle, T.K. (Eds.), *Contexts for Prehistoric Exchange*. Academic, New York, pp. 53–81.

Font, B., López-Polín, L., Ollé, A., 2010. Description and characterization of the natural alteration of chert artefacts from Atapuerca (Burgos, Spain), Cansaladeta (Tarragona, Spain) and Orgnac 3 (Ardèche, France). *Annali dell'Università di Ferrara, Mus. Sci. Nat.* 6, 103–110. <https://doi.org/10.15160/1824-2707/418>

Forbis, R.G., 1978. Some Facets of Communal Hunting. *Plains Anthropologist* 23, 3–8. <https://doi.org/10.1080/2052546.1978.11908895>

Gabarró, J.M., García-Antón, M.D., Giralt, S., Mallol, C., Sala, R., 1999. Análisis de la captación de las materias primas lítica en el conjunto técnico del Modo 2 de Galería. In: Carbonell, E., Rosas, A., Díez Fernández-Lomana, J.C. (Eds.), *Atapuerca: Ocupaciones Humanas y Paleoeología Del Yacimiento de Galería*. Junta de Castilla y León. Consejería de Educación y Cultura., pp. 283–297.

García-Antón, M.D., 2016a. La captación, selección y gestión de recursos líticos en la Prehistoria: Una visión diacrónica del uso del territorio y sus recursos en el entorno de la sierra de Atapuerca (Burgos) durante el Pleistoceno inferior y medio. *Universitat Rovira i Virgili*.

García-Antón, M.D., 2016b. Puesta al día de los conocimientos sobre las formaciones silíceas del entorno de los yacimientos de la Sierra de Atapuerca. *Cuadernos de Prehistoria de la Universidad de Granada* 26, 53–79.

García-Antón, M.D., Mosquera, M., 2007. Données préliminaires sur des aires d'approvisionnement et de selection des matières premières lithiques dans les occupations du Pleistocene moyen du niveau TD10-1. In: Moncel, M.H., Moigne, A.-M., Arzarello, M., Peretto, C. (Eds.), *Aires d'approvisionnement en Matières Premières et Aires d'approvisionnement en Ressources Alimentaires. Approche Intégrée Des Comportements*. BAR International Series 1725. Archaeopress, Oxford, pp. 171–185.

García-Antón, M.D., Morant Sabater, N., Mallol Duque, C., 2002. L'approvisionnement en matières premières lithiques au Pléistocène inférieur et moyen dans la Sierra de Atapuerca, Burgos (Espagne). *L'Anthropologie* 106, 41–55. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0003-5521\(02\)01086-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0003-5521(02)01086-5)

García-Medrano, P., Ollé, A., Mosquera, M., Cáceres, I., Díez, C., Carbonell, E., 2014. The earliest Acheulean technology at Atapuerca (Burgos, Spain): oldest levels of the

Galería site (GII Unit). *Quaternary International* 353, 170-194.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quaint.2014.03.053>

García-Medrano, P., Ollé, A., Mosquera, M., Cáceres, I., Carbonell, E., 2015. The nature of technological changes: The Middle Pleistocene stone tool assemblages from Galería and Gran Dolina subunit TD10.1. *Quaternary International* 368, 92–111.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quaint.2015.03.006>

García-Medrano, P., Cáceres, I., Ollé, A., Carbonell, E., 2017. The occupational pattern of the Galería site (Atapuerca, Spain): A technological perspective. *Quaternary International* 433, 363–378. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quaint.2015.11.013>

Garvey, R., 2015. A Model of Lithic Raw Material Procurement. In: Goodale, N., Andrefsky, W.J. (Eds.), *Lithic Technological Systems and Evolutionary Theory*. pp. 156–171.

Geneste, J. M., 1988. Les industries de la grotte Vaufray : technologie du débitage, économie et circulation de la matière première. In: Rigaud, J.P. (Ed.), *La Grotte Vaufray. Paléoenvironnement, Chronologie, Activités Humaines. Mémoire de la Société Préhistorique Française*, XIX, pp. 441–519.

Geneste, J.-M., 1991. L'approvisionnement en matières premières dans les systèmes de production lithique: La dimension spatiale de la technologie. *Treballs d'Arqueologia I*, 15–18.

Goodyear, A.C., 1993. Tool Kit Entropy and Bipolar Reduction: a Study of Interassemblage Lithic Variability Among Paleoindian Sites in the Northeastern United States. *North American Archaeologist* 14, 1–24.

Gould, R.A., Sagers, S., 1985. Lithic Procurement in Central Australia: A Closer Look at Binford's Idea of Embeddedness in Archaeology. *American Antiquity* 50, 117–136.
<https://doi.org/10.2307/280637>

Hiscock, P., 2009. Reduction, Recycling, and Raw Material Procurement in Western Arnhem Land, Australia. In: Adams, B., Blades, B.S. (Eds.), *Lithic Materials and Paleolithic Societies*. Blackwell Publishing Ltd, pp. 78–93.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/9781444311976.ch6>

- Huguet, R., Rodríguez-Álvarez, X.P., Martín-Torres, M., Vallverdú, J., López-García, J.M., Lozano, M., Terradillos-Bernal, M., Expósito, I., Ollé, A., Santos, E., Saladié, P., de Lombera-Hermida, A., Moreno-Ribas, E., Martín-Francés, L., Allué, E., Núñez-Lahuerta, C., Van der Made, J., Galán, J., Blain, H.A., Cáceres, I., Rodríguez-Hidalgo, A., Bargalló, A., Mosquera, M., Parés, J.M., Marín, J., Pineda, A., Lordkipanidze, D., Margveslashvili, A., Arsuaga, J.L., Carbonell, E., Bermúdez de Castro, J.M., 2025. The earliest human face of Western Europe. *Nature* 640. 707-713 <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-025-08681-0>
- Kelly, R.L., 2013. The lifeways of hunter-gatherers. *The Foraging Spectrum*. Cambridge University Press.
- Key, A., Bartkowiak, T., Macdonald, D.A., Mietlinski, P., Gapinski, B., de la Torre, I., Stemp, W.J., 2024. Quantifying Edge Sharpness on Stone Flakes: Comparing Mechanical and Micro-Geometric Definitions Across Multiple Raw Materials from Olduvai Gorge (Tanzania). *Journal of Archaeological Method and Theory* 31, 51–74. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10816-022-09596-0>
- Kuhn, S.L., 1994. A Formal Approach to the Design and Assembly of Mobile Toolkits. *American Antiquity* 59, 426–442. <https://doi.org/10.2307/282456>
- Li, F., Kuhn, S.L., Chen, F. you, Gao, X., 2016. Raw material economies and mobility patterns in the Late Paleolithic at Shuidonggou locality 2, north China. *Journal of Anthropological Archaeology* 43, 83–93. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaa.2016.05.008>
- Lucas, G., 2012. *Understanding the archaeological record*. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511845772>
- Lucero, G.F., Castro, S.C., Cortegoso, V., 2021. GIS modeling of lithic procurement in highlands: Archaeological and actualistic approach in the Andes. *Journal of Archaeological Science: Reports* 38. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jasrep.2021.103026>
- Luedtke, B., 1992. The Nature of Chert. In: *An Archaeologist's Guide to Chert and Flint*. Cotsen Institute of Archaeology Press at UCLA. <https://doi.org/10.2307/jj.13609938>
- Mallol, C., 1999. The selection of Lithic Raw Materials in the Lower and Middle Pleistocene Levels TD6 and TD10A of Gran Dolina (Sierra de Atapuerca, Burgos, Spain). *Journal of Anthropological Research* 55, 385–407.
- McCall, G.S., 2012. Ethnoarchaeology and the Organization of Lithic Technology. *Journal of Archaeological Research* 20, 157–203. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10814-011-9056-z>

Mears, P., Wilson, L., 2023. A game of two halves: Looking for evidence for both embedded and direct procurement in a simulated dataset. *Journal of Lithic Studies* 10(2), 19 p. <https://doi.org/10.2218/jls.7248>

Meignen, L., Delagnes, A., Bourguignon, L., 2009. Patterns of lithic material procurement and transformation during the Middle Paleolithic in Western Europe. In: *Lithic Materials and Paleolithic Societies*. pp. 15–24. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781444311976.ch2>

Metcalfé, D., Barlow, K.R., 1992. A Model for Exploring the Optimal Trade-off between Field Processing and Transport. *American Anthropologist* 94, 340–356.

Moncel, M.H., Daujeard, C., 2012. The variability of the Middle Palaeolithic on the right bank of the Middle Rhône Valley (southeast France): Technical traditions or functional choices? *Quaternary International* 247, 103–124. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quaint.2010.10.030>

Moreno, D., Falguères, C., Pérez-González, A., Duval, M., Voinchet, P., Benito-Calvo, A., Ortega, A.I., Bahain, J.J., Sala, R., Carbonell, E., Bermúdez de Castro, J.M., Arsuaga, J.L., 2012. ESR chronology of alluvial deposits in the Arlanzón valley (Atapuerca, Spain): Contemporaneity with Atapuerca Gran Dolina site. *Quaternary Geochronology* 10, 418–423. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quageo.2012.04.018>

Moreno, D., Falguères, C., Pérez-González, A., Voinchet, P., Ghaleb, B., Despriée, J., Bahain, J.-J., Sala, R., Carbonell, E., Bermúdez de Castro, J.M., Arsuaga, J.L., 2015. New radiometric dates on the lowest stratigraphical section (TD1 to TD6) of Gran Dolina site (Atapuerca, Spain). *Quaternary Geochronology* 30, 535–540. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quageo.2015.05.007>

Mosquera, M., Ollé, A., Pérez-González, A., Rodríguez, X.P., Vaquero, M., Vergès, J.M., Carbonell, E., 2007. Valle de las Orquídeas: Un yacimiento al aire libre del Pleistoceno superior en la Sierra de Atapuerca (Burgos). *Trabajos de Prehistoria* 64, 143–155. <https://doi.org/10.3989/tp.2007.v64.i2.113>

Mosquera, M., Ollé, A., Rodríguez-Álvarez, X.P., Carbonell, E., 2018. Shedding light on the early Pleistocene of TD6 (Gran Dolina, Atapuerca, Spain): The technological sequence and occupational inferences. *PLoS ONE* 13(1):e0190889. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0190889>

Mosquera, M., Ollé, A., Saladié, P., Arroyo, A., Asryan, L., Bargalló, A., Lombera-Hermida, A. de, Fernández-Marchena, J.L., García-Medrano, P., Lombao, D., Rodríguez-Hidalgo, A., Soto, M., Vallverdú, J., Arteaga-Brieba, A., Villalobos, J., Yeşilova, G.C., Carbonell, E., 2024. Intriguing occupations at Gran Dolina (Atapuerca, Spain): the Acheulean subunits TD10.3 and TD10.4. *Journal of Paleolithic Archaeology* 7, 6 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41982-024-00171-5>

Navazo, M., Colina, A., Domínguez-Bella, S., Benito-Calvo, A., 2008. Raw stone material supply for Upper Pleistocene settlements in Sierra de Atapuerca (Burgos, Spain): flint characterization using petrographic and geochemical techniques. *Journal of Archaeological Science* 35, 1961–1973. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jas.2007.12.009>

Nelson, M.C., 1991. The study of Technological Organization. *Archaeological Method and Theory* 31, 57–100.

Newman, J.R., 1994. The effects of distance on lithic material reduction technology. *Journal of Field Archaeology* 21, 491–501. <https://doi.org/10.1179/009346994797175541>

Nora, D., Marreiros, J., Gneisinger, W., Pedergrana, A., Pereira, T., 2025. The dichotomy of human decision-making: An experimental assessment of stone tool efficiency. *PLOS ONE* 20. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0327215>

Olivé, A., Ramírez Merino, J.L., Ortega, L.I., Hernández Samaniego, A., Elorza, M., 1990. Mapa Geológico de España: Hoja de Belorado 201 (20-10). Serie MAGNA. E. 1:50.000. Instituto Geológico y Minero de España, Madrid.

Ollé, A., Mosquera, M., Rodríguez, X.P., Lombera-Hermida, A. de, García-Antón, M.D., García-Medrano, P., Peña, L., Menéndez, L., Navazo, M., Terradillos, M., Bargalló, A., Márquez, B., Sala, R., Carbonell, E., 2013. The Early and Middle Pleistocene technological record from Sierra de Atapuerca (Burgos, Spain). *Quaternary International* 295, 138–167. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quaint.2011.11.009>

Ortega, A.I., Benito-Calvo, A., Pérez-González, A., Carbonell, E., Bermúdez de Castro, J.M., Arsuaga, J.L., 2014. Atapuerca Karst and its Palaeoanthropological Sites. In: Gutiérrez, F., Gutiérrez, M. (Eds.), *Landscapes and Landforms of Spain*. Springer, pp. 101–110. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-017-8628-7_8

Ortega Martínez, A.I., 2009. La evolución geomorfológica del Karst de la Sierra de Atapuerca (Burgos) y su relación con los yacimientos Pleistocenos que contiene. Universidad de Burgos.

Pedergrana, A., García-Antón, M.D., Ollé, A., 2017. Structural study of two quartzite varieties from the Utrillas facies formation (Olmos de Atapuerca, Burgos, Spain): From a petrographic characterisation to a functional analysis design. *Quaternary International* 433, 163–178. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quaint.2015.06.031>

Perreault, C., 2019. *The Quality of the Archaeological Record*. University of Chicago Press. <https://doi.org/10.7208/chicago/9780226631011.003.0005>

Pineda, A., Arce, J.M., 1997. Mapa Geológico de España escala 1:50.000. 2a Serie (MAGNA). Hoja de Burgos, 200.

Pop, C.M., Wilson, L., Browne, C.L., 2022. Evaluating landscape knowledge and lithic resource selection at the French Middle Paleolithic site of the Bau de l'Aubesier. *Journal of Human Evolution* 166, 103152. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhevol.2022.103152>

Pyke, G.H., 1984. Optimal Foraging Theory: A Critical Review. *Annual Review of Ecology and Systematics* 15, 523–575. <https://doi.org/10.1146/ANNUREV.ES.15.110184.002515>

Pyke, G.H., Pulliam, H.R., Charnov, E.L., 1977. Optimal Foraging: A Selective Review of Theory and Tests. *The Quarterly Review of Biology* 52, 137–154. <https://doi.org/10.1086/409852>

Raichlen, D.A., Wood, B.M., Gordon, A.B., Mabulla, A.Z., Marlowe, F.W., Pontzer, H., 2014. Evidence of Lévy walk foraging patterns in human hunter–gatherers. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 111(2), 728–733.

Renfrew, C., 1977. Alternative models for exchange and spatial distribution. In: Earle, T.K., Ericson, J.E. (Eds.), *Exchange Systems in Prehistory*. Academic Press, New York, pp. 71–90. <https://doi.org/10.1016/b978-0-12-227650-7.50010-9>

Rodríguez, J., Burjachs, F., Cuenca-Bescós, G., García, N., Van der Made, J., Pérez-González, A., Blain, H.A., Expósito, I., López-García, J.M., García-Antón, M.D., Allué, E., Cáceres, I., Huguet, R., Mosquera, M., Ollé, A., Rosell, J., Parés, J.M., Rodríguez-Álvarez, X.P., Díez, C., Rofes, J., Sala, R., Saladié, P., Vallverdú, J., Bennàsar, M.L.,

Blasco, R., Bermúdez de Castro, J.M., Carbonell, E., 2011. One million years of cultural evolution in a stable environment at Atapuerca (Burgos, Spain). *Quaternary Science Reviews* 30, 1396–1412. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quascirev.2010.02.021>

Rodríguez-Gómez, G., Rodríguez-Hidalgo, A., Saladié, P., Van der Made, J., Marín, J., Ollé, A., Mosquera, M., Bermúdez de Castro, J.M., Arsuaga, J.L., Carbonell, E., 2025. Ecologically sustainable human exploitation of the Gran Dolina TD10.2 bison (Sierra de Atapuerca, Spain). *Scientific Reports* 15, 23178. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-025-01928-w>

Rodríguez-Hidalgo, A., 2015. *Dinámicas Subsistenciales durante el Pleistoceno Medio en la sierra de Atapuerca: Los conjuntos arqueológicos de TD10.1 y TD10.2*. Universitat Rovira i Virgili.

Rodríguez-Hidalgo, A., 2016. Subsistence Dynamics during the Lower Paleolithic in Gran Dolina Cave (Atapuerca, Spain). *Mitteilungen der Gesellschaft für Urgeschichte* 25, 11–48.

Rodríguez-Hidalgo, A., Rivals, F., Saladié, P., Carbonell, E., 2016. Season of bison mortality in TD10.2 bone bed at Gran Dolina site (Atapuerca): Integrating tooth eruption, wear, and microwear methods. *Journal of Archaeological Science: Reports* 6, 780–789. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jasrep.2015.11.033>

Rodríguez-Hidalgo, A., Saladié, P., Ollé, A., Arsuaga, J.L., Bermúdez de Castro, J.M., Carbonell, E., 2017. Human predatory behavior and the social implications of communal hunting based on evidence from the TD10.2 bison bone bed at Gran Dolina (Atapuerca, Spain). *Journal of Human Evolution* 105, 89–122. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhevol.2017.01.007>

Romagnoli, F., Bargalló, A., Chacón, M.G., Gómez de Soler, B., Vaquero, M., 2017. Testing a hypothesis about the importance of the quality of raw material on technological changes at Abric Romaní (Capellades, Spain): Some considerations using a high-resolution techno-economic perspective. *Journal of Lithic Studies* 3, 1–25. <https://doi.org/10.2218/jls.v3i2.1443>

Santamaría, M., Navazo, M., Benito-Calvo, A., Alonso, R., Lopez, G.I., Carbonell, E., 2021. Atapuerca Neanderthal landscape at Fuente Mudarra site in Burgos, Spain, during

Marine Isotope Stages 5-3. *Quaternary Research* 99, 248–269.
<https://doi.org/10.1017/qua.2020.65>

Santamaría, M., Navazo, M., Arnold, L.J., Benito-Calvo, A., Demuro, M., Carbonell, E., 2023. Low-cost technologies in a rich ecological context: Hotel California open-air site at Sierra de Atapuerca, Burgos, Spain. *Journal of Quaternary Science* 38, 658–684.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/jqs.3501>

Schmidt, P., Pappas, I., Porraz, G., Berthold, C., Nickel, K.G., 2024. The driving force behind tool-stone selection in the African Middle Stone Age. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* 121(10) e2318560121.
<https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2318560121>

Sharon, G., 2008. The impact of raw material on Acheulian large flake production. *Journal of Archaeological Science* 35, 1329–1344.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jas.2007.09.004>

Shick, K.D., 1987. Modeling the formation of Early Stone Age artifact concentrations. *Journal of Human Evolution* 16, 789–807. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0047-2484\(87\)90024-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/0047-2484(87)90024-8)

Shimelmitz, R., Kuhn, S.L., Weinstein-Evron, M., 2020. The evolution of raw procurement strategies: A view from the deep sequence of Tabun Cave, Israel. *Journal of Human Evolution* 143, 102787. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhevol.2020.102787>

Smith, E.A., Bettinger, R.L., Bishop, C.A., Blundell, V., Cashdan, E., Casimir, M.J., Christenson, A.L., Cox, B., Dyson-Hudson, R., Hayden, B., Richerson, P.J., Roth, E.A., Simms, S.R., Stini, W.A., 1983. Anthropological Applications of Optimal Foraging Theory: A Critical Review [and Comments and Reply]. *Current Anthropology* 24(5), 625–651.

Sossa-Ríos, S., Mayor, A., Sánchez-Romero, L., Mallol, C., Vaquero, M., Hernández, C.M., 2024. The Time of the Stones: A Call for Palimpsest Dissection to Explore Lithic Record Formation Processes. *Journal of Archaeological Method and Theory* 31, 2188–2238. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10816-024-09666-5>

Soto, M., Gómez de Soler, B., Vallverdú, J., 2018. The chert abundance ratio (CAR): a new parameter for interpreting Palaeolithic raw material procurement. *Archaeological*

and Anthropological Sciences 10, 2027–2046. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12520-017-0516-3>

Soto, M., Arteaga-Brieba, A., Mosquera, M., Ollé, A., Vallverdú, J., 2021. Neogene chert exploitation at sub-unit TD10.2 (Atapuerca, Burgos). In: Gómez de Soler, B., Soto, M., Chacón, M.G., Soares, M. (Eds.), *Rock and Roll: 13th International Symposium on Knappable Materials*. Tarragona, p. 90.

Speth, J.D., 2013. Thoughts about hunting: Some things we know and some things we don't know. *Quaternary International* 297, 176–185. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quaint.2012.12.005>

Steele, D.G., Baker, B.W., 1993. Multiple predation: a definitive human hunting strategy. In: Hudson, J.L. (Ed.), *From Bones to Behavior: Ethnoarchaeological and Experimental Contributions to the Interpretation of Faunal Remains*. University at Carbondale, Southern Illinois, pp. 9–37.

Stout, D., Quade, J., Semaw, S., Rogers, M.J., Levin, N.E., 2005. Raw material selectivity of the earliest stone toolmakers at Gona, Afar, Ethiopia. *Journal of Human Evolution* 48, 365–380. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhevol.2004.10.006>

Taçon, P.S.C., 1991. The power of stone: Symbolic aspects of stone use and tool development in western Arnhem Land, Australia. *Antiquity* 65, 192–207. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0003598X00079655>

Terradillos-Bernal, M., Rodríguez-Álvarez, X.P., 2014. The influence of raw material qualities in the lithic technology of Gran Dolina (Units TD6 and TD10) and Galería (Sierra de Atapuerca, Burgos, Spain): A view from experimental archeology. *Comptes rendus - Palevol* 13, 527–542. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.crpv.2014.02.002>

Terradillos-Bernal, M., Rodríguez-Álvarez, X.P., 2017. The influence of raw material quality on the characteristics of the lithic tool edges from the Atapuerca sites (Burgos, Spain). *Quaternary International* 433, 211–223. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quaint.2015.10.122>

Terradillos-Bernal, M., Zorrilla-Revilla, G., Rodríguez-Álvarez, X.P., 2022. To be or not to be a lithic tool: analysing the limestone pieces of Sima del Elefante (Sierra de Atapuerca, northern Spain). *Archaeological and Anthropological Sciences* 14, 189. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12520-022-01643-x>

Tomasso, A., Porraz, G., 2016. Hunter-gatherer mobility and embedded raw-material procurement strategies in the Mediterranean Upper Paleolithic. *Evolutionary Anthropology* 25, 164–174. <https://doi.org/10.1002/evan.21488>

Torrence, R., 1983. Time budgeting and hunter-gatherer technology. In: Bailey, G. (Ed.), *Hunter-Gatherer Economy in Prehistory: A European Perspective*. Cambridge University Press, pp. 11–22.

Torrence, R., 1989. Retooling: towards a behavioral theory of stone tools. In: Torrence, R. (Ed.), *Time, Energy and Stone Tools*. Cambridge University Press, pp. 57–66.

Turq, A., Roebroeks, W., Bourguignon, L., Faivre, J.-P., 2013. The fragmented character of Middle Palaeolithic stone tool technology. *Journal of Human Evolution* 65, 641–655. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhevol.2013.07.014>

Vaquero, M., Romagnoli, F., 2018. Searching for Lazy People: the Significance of Expedient Behavior in the Interpretation of Paleolithic Assemblages. *Journal of Archaeological Method and Theory* 25, 334–367. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10816-017-9339-x>

Warnitz, L., Martín-Perea, D.M., Ollé, A., Saladié, P., Rodríguez-Hidalgo, A., Mosquera, M., Parés, J.M., Carbonell, E., Vallverdú, J., 2025. Landscape evolution and chronostratigraphic correlations of the cave entrance depositional environments and palaeosols of the Gran Dolina unit TD10 (Sierra de Atapuerca, Spain). *Catena* 258, 109191. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.catena.2025.109191>

Wilson, L., 2007a. Terrain difficulty as a factor in raw material procurement in the Middle Palaeolithic of France. *Journal of Field Archaeology* 32, 315–324. <https://doi.org/10.1179/009346907791071539>

Wilson, L., 2007b. Understanding prehistoric Lithic raw material selection: Application of a gravity model. *Journal of Archaeological Method and Theory* 14, 388–411. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10816-007-9042-4>

Wilson, L., 2011. Raw material economics in their environmental context: An example from the Middle Palaeolithic of southern France. In: Wilson, L. (Ed.), *Human Interactions with the Geosphere: The Geoarchaeological Perspective*. The Geological Society Publishing House, London, pp. 163–180.

Wilson, L., Browne, C.L., 2014. Change in raw material selection and subsistence behaviour through time at a Middle Palaeolithic site in southern France. *Journal of Human Evolution* 75, 28–39. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhevol.2013.12.018>

Wilson, L., Browne, C.L., Texier, P.J., 2018. Provisioning on the periphery: Middle Palaeolithic raw material supply strategies on the outer edge of a territory at La Combette (France). *Journal of Archaeological Science: Reports* 21, 87–98. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jasrep.2018.07.001>

Zornoza-Indart, A., López-Arce, P., López-Polín, L., 2017. Archaeological chert artifacts from Atapuerca sites (Burgos, Spain): Characterization, causes of decay and selection of compatible consolidating products. *Conservar Patrimonio* 36, 20–35. <https://doi.org/10.14568/cp2019037>

Zornoza-Indart, A., López-Arce, P., López-Polín, L., 2021. Durability of traditional and new nanoparticle based consolidating products for the treatment of archaeological stone tools: Chert artifacts from Atapuerca sites (Burgos, Spain). *Journal of Cultural Heritage* 24, 9–21.